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NANOTECNOLOGIE**

**ADSORPTION, METALATION AND MAGNETIC
PROPERTIES OF TETRA PHENYL PORPHYRINS ON
METAL SURFACES**

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Abstract

Traditional semiconductor technology will reach a size limit within the next few years. A possible solution could be the use of organic molecules in technological applications as single functional units in metal-organic based devices; the success of this approach strongly depends on the understanding of the behaviour of these molecules on metallic surfaces. The interaction with metallic substrates and the interaction between the molecules themselves determine the electronic and magnetic properties of the system, and it is thus of fundamental interest to study these metal-organic interfaces both in the case of single molecules and layer structures.

In this thesis, an extensive study of the electronic and magnetic properties of tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (2H-TPP) molecules adsorbed on metal surfaces is reported.

By means of scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) we studied the adsorption geometry of these molecules on the Au(111), Ag(111) and Cu(100) surfaces. By using X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS) and near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) spectroscopy, a temperature-induced conformational adaptation reaction of the 2H-TPP molecules adsorbed on the Au(111) and Ag(111) surfaces, upon annealing at 550 K, is described. A possible dehydrogenation reaction, with the formation of new C-C bonds, could explain the rotation of the molecule phenyl rings parallel to the surface plane and the associated increasing in the molecule-substrate interaction.

In-situ metalation of porphyrins in ultra-high vacuum is obtained by two methods: in the first one, the metalation of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) is achieved by direct metal evaporation (Mn, Rh and Fe) on the molecular layer; in the second case we report the self-metalation of 2H-TPP through the coordination with a metal atom from the Fe(110) and Al(111) substrates. In addition, we investigated the effects of metalation and temperature-induced conformational adaptation on the molecule-substrate interaction, by means of XPS and NEXAFS, in the case of CoTPP on Ag(111).

The magnetic properties resulting from the metal coordination are studied by X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD). Here, a description of the magnetic coupling of a MnTPP/Cl single layer with a Fe(110) ferromagnetic substrate is disclosed. Moreover, we focused on the study of the magnetic properties and exchange coupling of two layer of molecule and a ferromagnetic thin film. In the case of a MnTPP layer on FeTPP/Fe(110) the magnetic coupling extends to the second layer of molecules, for which the magnetization is opposite with respect to the substrate.

Sommario

Le tradizionali tecnologie utilizzate nell'industria dei semiconduttori raggiungeranno, entro breve tempo, il limite nella miniaturizzazione dei loro componenti. Una possibile alternativa potrebbe venire dall'utilizzo di molecole organiche come singole unità funzionali in dispositivi metallo-organici; d'altra parte il successo di questo approccio dipende in maniera sostanziale dalla comprensione del comportamento di queste molecole sulle superfici dei metalli. L'interazione con il substrato metallico e la stessa interazione tra le molecole determinano le proprietà elettroniche e magnetiche di questi sistemi, ed è dunque di fondamentale interesse lo studio di queste interfacce metallo-organiche sia nel caso di singole molecole che di strutture più complesse.

In questa tesi è riportato uno studio dettagliato delle proprietà elettroniche e magnetiche di tetra-fenil-porfirine (2H-TPP) adsorbite su superfici metalliche.

Attraverso la microscopia a scansione a effetto tunnel (STM) è stata studiata la geometria di adsorbimento di queste molecole sulle superfici Au(111), Ag(111) e Cu(100). Utilizzando le spettroscopie XPS (*X-ray photoemission spectroscopy*) e NEXAFS (*near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure*) è descritta la reazione di adattamento conformazionale delle 2H-TPP adsorbite sulle superfici Au(111) e Ag(111) a seguito del processo di *annealing* a 550 K. Una possibile reazione di de-idrogenazione, con la formazione di nuovi legami C-C, può spiegare la rotazione dei gruppi fenili della molecola verso la superficie e l'aumento dell'interazione molecola-substrato ad esso associato.

La metallazione *in-situ* delle porfirine in ultra-alto vuoto è ottenuta in due modi: nel primo, la metallazione delle 2H-TPP su Ag(111) è raggiunta con la diretta evaporazione del metallo (Mn, Rh e Fe) sullo strato di molecole; nel secondo caso, sulle superfici Fe(110) e Al(111) la metallazione avviene automaticamente tramite la coordinazione della 2H-TPP con un atomo della superficie. Inoltre, gli effetti della metallazione e dell'adattamento conformazionale sull'interazione molecola-substrato sono stati studiati, tramite XPS e NEXAFS, nel caso di CoTPP su Ag(111).

Le proprietà magnetiche risultanti dalla coordinazione della molecola con un atomo metallico sono state studiate per mezzo della tecnica XMCD (*X-ray magnetic circular dichroism*). In particolare, viene descritto l'accoppiamento magnetico di un singolo strato di MnTPP/Cl con un substrato ferromagnetico Fe(110). Inoltre, ci si è focalizzati sullo studio delle proprietà magnetiche tra due strati di molecole e un film sottile ferromagnetico. Nel caso specifico di MnTPP su FeTPP/Fe(110) l'accoppiamento magnetico si estende al secondo strato di molecole, per il quale la magnetizzazione è opposta rispetto al substrato.

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Chapter 1

Introduction: Molecular magnetism

The miniaturization of electronic devices, starting from the 1950s, has progressed at a fast rate. The number of functional units integrated in single devices increased exponentially with time, a trend known as Moore's law [1], with a simultaneous reduction in their size and energy consumption. The semiconductor industry has been characterized by the constant pursuit of creating smaller functional units, while the science interest went at the same pace towards smaller physical systems, with the advent of nanotechnology.

Traditionally, the production of such devices has been based on the so-called *top-down* approach [2], in which big structures are made smaller. This has been achieved by the adaptation of traditional principles and techniques to a smaller scale, such as lithography using electron beam [3] or ultraviolet and X-ray radiation [4]. However, despite the successful technological efforts adopted, in the last years, these methods reached overcoming technological limits, while their operating costs rapidly increased. Besides this, approaching the nano-scale, quantum effects play a dominant role and the same operational principles of these devices, once they are constituted just by few atoms, are not more valid, and a switch to a new technology is required [5].

An alternative approach consists in the assembly of small building blocks to produce functional units, a method which is referred to as *bottom-up* [2, 6]. Organic molecules represent one of the most promising class of materials in this sense and their use in nano-fabrication methods presents some key advantages [7]. Beside their small size, in the order of few nanometres, they are structurally identical and the interaction and recognition between them can lead to the formation of self-assembled structures [8–13]. Moreover, through molecular synthesis chemistry, different functional groups can be substituted, allowing to introduce and control new properties of the molecule [14].

Organic molecules such as porphyrins and phthalocyanines can be deposited in the sub-monolayer regime on single crystal surfaces in ultra high vacuum and

geometrically ordered structures can be obtained from this procedure [15]. The unsaturated molecular macrocycle brings synthetic tailorability for these chemical systems thanks to the presence of different positions in which functional groups can be substituted [16]. By varying the composition and geometry of these molecules, it is possible to control their structural, bonding, transport, and optical properties.

Taking advantage of the flexibility in choosing the substituents, in combination with the presence of active sites of interactions with metals, this kind of molecules can be used to fabricate two-dimensional arrays of metallic centres with nanometric spacing, making them promising candidates for applications in emerging fields like spintronics and molecular electronics, as building blocks for molecular-based devices with controllable and tunable properties [17, 18], for novel metal–organic architectures in solid-state chemistry and in molecular engineering [13, 16, 19–23] as well as to form patterned surfaces for catalytic, magnetic, optoelectronic, and sensing materials [24–31].

Several metals can be efficiently coordinated to porphyrins by in-situ metal evaporation [25–27, 32–37], [[1]], or by simply picking-up substrate atoms or ad-atoms which coordinate with the molecule macrocycle, forming a metallo-porphyrin [38–45], [[12]].

Recent developments in the field of surface magnetism, with the possible applications of some paramagnetic metal-organic macrocycle molecules as switchable elements in molecular spintronic devices [46–48], have generated much interest into the structural and magnetic properties of these molecules [20, 49–55, 55–71].

Experimental techniques such as X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) and X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD), due to their sensitivity and chemical selectivity, are ideal to probe the electronic and magnetic properties of the metal-organic interface.

This thesis will address the study of tetra-phenyl-porphyrins on metal surfaces, focusing on the adsorption and metalation processes and the resulting electronic and magnetic properties of the system.

In chapter 2 the experimental techniques related to the reported results are briefly described. In addition, in section 2.1.2 it will be presented a new approach for the thermal drift correction in scanning probe microscopy images.

Chapter 3 addresses the adsorption and self-assembly of porphyrins on metal surfaces in ultra high vacuum (UHV). Scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) micrographs of tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (TPP) self-assembled monolayers on Au(111), Ag(111) and Cu(100) crystal surfaces are presented in section 3.2. In Sections 3.3 and 3.4 the conformational adaptation reaction that the porphyrin monolayer undergoes upon annealing is described, in the case of adsorption on the Au(111) and Ag(111) surfaces, respectively.

The metalation process of tetra-phenyl-porphyrin in UHV is discussed in Chapter 4, for the two metalation processes investigated, namely metal evaporation

(Section 4.2) and metal atom picking-up (Section 4.3). The effects of metalation and conformational adaptation on the molecule-substrate interaction is addressed in Section 4.4.

Chapter 5 is devoted to the investigation of the magnetic properties of tetraphenyl-porphyrins arising after their metalation. In particular, the magnetic coupling of a single layer of TPP on a ferromagnetic substrate is reported in Section 5.2, while in Section 5.3 the magnetic coupling between two layers of porphyrins is reported for the first time.

Conclusions are summarized in Chapter 6 and a list of publications related to this thesis is given in Appendix A.

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Chapter 2

Experimental background. Techniques and data analysis

In this chapter will be briefly reviewed the experimental techniques used throughout this thesis in order to give an overview of their main features. Detailed information on the principles and the methods are provided in the references. In addition, an approach for the correction of thermal drift in scanning probe microscopy techniques is derived.

2.1 STM

2.1.1 Technique

In scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) a small metal tip is brought near enough to a conducting surface so that the electron tunnelling through the vacuum between them is finite and measurable.

For electronic states at the Fermi level, the surface-vacuum interface represents a potential barrier whose height is equal to the work function ϕ .

In first-order perturbation theory the tunnelling current is given by [1]:

$$I = \frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{\mu, \nu} \{f(E_\mu)[1 - f(E_\nu)] - f(E_\nu)[1 - f(E_\mu)]\} |M_{\mu\nu}|^2 \delta(E_\nu + V - E_\mu) \quad (2.1)$$

where $f(E)$ is the Fermi distribution, V is the applied voltage, $M_{\mu\nu}$ is the tunnelling matrix element between states ψ_μ of the probe and ψ_ν of the surface, and E_μ and E_ν are their respective energies in the absence of tunnelling.

At high temperatures the negative term takes into account for inverse tunnelling. Since the experiments are performed at room temperature or below and at small

voltages, in this contest the Fermi functions can be replaced by its zero-temperature values; so in the limit of small applied voltages and temperatures the expression can be approximated by:

$$I = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} e^2 V \sum_{\mu, \nu} |M_{\mu\nu}|^2 \delta(E_\mu - E_F) \delta(E_\nu - E_F) \quad (2.2)$$

The evaluation of the matrix element $|M_{\mu\nu}|$ is not simple, but Bardeen [2] has shown that, under certain assumptions, it can be expressed as

$$M_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \int dS \cdot (\psi_\mu \nabla \psi_\nu - \psi_\nu \nabla \psi_\mu) \quad (2.3)$$

where the integral is over any surface lying entirely within the barrier region.

The actual atomic structure of the tip is generally not known and one must therefore adopt a model. The ideal STM tip would consist of a mathematical point source of current at position r_t ; in this case the tunnelling current for very small voltages reduces to [3, 4]

$$I \propto \sum_{\nu} |\psi_\nu(r_t)|^2 \delta(E_\nu - E_F) \equiv \rho(r_t, E_F) \quad (2.4)$$

This is nothing but local density of states (LDOS) of the sample at E_F evaluated in the absence of the tip, but at the position which the tip will occupy. Thus, within this model, STM can be simple interpreted as measuring the charge density from the states at the Fermi level of the bare surface, without referencing to the complex tip-sample system.

Equation (2.4) remains valid, regardless of the tip size, so long as the the tunnelling matrix elements can be approximated by those of an s -wave tip wave function [3].

At larger voltages it seems reasonable to generalize (2.4) to an expression such as

$$I \sim \int_{E_F}^{E_F + eV} \rho(r_t, E) dE \quad (2.5)$$

In this equation the energy dependence of the matrix elements and the tip density of states are not taken into account; moreover the finite voltage changes the potential, and hence the wave-functions, outside the surface. Nevertheless this approximations are reasonable as long as the voltage is much smaller than the work function.

2.1.2 Data analysis: a new procedure for drift correction in scanning probe microscopy

Images obtained by scanning probe techniques are often found to be affected by distortions due to thermal drift. This is especially true when the measurements are performed at ambient temperature, turning very challenging the determination of distances and angles. This thermal drift usually originates from a different coefficient of thermal expansion between the different part of the measuring device and the sample. Its effect is, in general, not negligible: considering a typical coefficient of thermal expansion of 10^{-5} K^{-1} , for the dimension of an STM device, a change in temperature of just 1 K/h results in a thermal drift of the order of $1.5 \text{ \AA}/\text{min}$. Thus drift correction is of fundamental importance in order to perform quantitative analysis and to determine precisely both distances and angles.

In order to reduce thermal drift, an useful approach is to place the scanner inside a cryostat or simply scan fast enough to make the thermal drift negligible [5–8]. However, these approaches not always can be applied, for example when it is required to investigate the system at room temperature. In these cases, drift corrections can be performed by (i) measuring drift velocities (for example by atom tracking) [9–12] or (ii) through comparison to expected structures [13–15]. In the former case, the approach is based on the comparison of two subsequent images, in the latter cases the exact knowledge of the geometry and dimension of the expected structure is required.

The approach described here combines the two methods and relies on the comparison of a periodic structure of known geometry (but unknown dimensions) between two counter-scanned images. Usually, in scanning probe microscopy, the simultaneous measurement of an image in the forward and backward directions is a common practice. In the imaging of periodic structures, by definition, is not possible to apply any drift correction that relies on the tracking of a stationary feature, in the absence of defects on the surface. However, in this case, one can take advantage of the presence of a periodic structure in order to calculate the drift by the comparison of the deformations between the two scanned images. In particular, in the following, an algorithm for the drift correction is derived. It relies on the analysis of the Fourier transform (FFT) of the STM images and, through their comparison, allows to calculate the correction factor that can be directly applied by a scaling and shearing procedure on the same images.

Methods

STM images are typically obtained by using forward (F), backward (B), up and down raster scanning. Considering Figure 2.1(a) the forward image (F) is constructed by left to right in the fast scan direction and top to bottom in the slow scan

Figure 2.1: (a) Construction of an SPM image. Without any drift the forward and backward images are identical. (b) Representation of the wave vectors in the reciprocal space for a square lattice. In the general case $a = Cb$ and $\gamma \neq \pi/2$.

Figure 2.2: Shearing and scaling distortions for the forward (green) and backward (blue) images resulting from an horizontal drift in the positive (a) and negative (b) directions. The shearing angle in x is indicated as ϕ .

direction, the backward image (B) by right to left in the fast scan direction and top to bottom in the slow scan direction. If no drift is present the two resulting images, and their fast Fourier transform (FFT), are exactly the same. Figure 2.1(b) represent the wave vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} in the reciprocal space for a periodic lattice. In the following x and y indicate the real space coordinates and a_x , a_y , b_x and b_y the reciprocal space components. In the presence of an horizontal drift z , positive in the left-to-right direction (Figure 2.2), the F (B) image will be scaled in x by $1 - z$ ($1 + z$) and sheared in y by $\tan \phi$ as described in Table 2.2. In the presence of vertical drift s , positive in the top-to-bottom direction (Figure 2.3), both F and B are scaled in y by $1 - s$ and sheared by $\tan \theta$ as indicated in Table 2.2.

In the general case, when a drift in both directions is present, the scaling factors (z , s) are applied to the real space images as indicated in Tables 2.1 and then

Figure 2.3: Shearing and scaling distortions for the forward (green) and backward (blue) images resulting from a vertical drift in the positive (a) and negative (b) directions. The shearing angle in y is indicated as θ .

Direction	Scaling factor
x_F	$(1 - z)$
x_B	$(1 + z)$
y_F	$(1 - s)$
y_B	$(1 - s)$

Table 2.1: Scaling factors in real space. Each dimension for the measured F and B real space images has to be multiplied by the appropriate scaling factor to obtain the correct scaling.

shearing factors ($\tan \theta$, $\tan \varphi$) as indicated in Table 2.2.

Considering that any scaling or shearing in the real space is rotated by 90° in reciprocal space, for the reciprocal wave vectors holds:

Forward:

$$a_x^F = a_x(1 - z) - a_y \tan \theta \quad (2.6a)$$

$$b_x^F = b_x(1 - z) + b_y \tan \theta \quad (2.6b)$$

$$a_y^F = a_y(1 - s) - a_x \tan \varphi \quad (2.6c)$$

$$b_y^F = b_y(1 - s) + b_x \tan \varphi \quad (2.6d)$$

Direction	Shearing factor	Sense
x_F	$\tan \varphi$	CCW $z < 0$ CW $z > 0$
x_B	$\tan \varphi$	CCW $z < 0$ CW $z > 0$
y_F	$\tan \theta$	CW $s < 0$ CCW $s > 0$
y_B	$\tan \theta$	CCW $s < 0$ CW $s > 0$

Table 2.2: Shearing factors in real space. The shearing factor has to be applied on the measured F and B real space images along the sense indicated (CW clockwise, CCW counter-clockwise), after the application of the scaling.

Backward:

$$a_x^B = a_x(1 + z) + a_y \tan \theta \quad (2.7a)$$

$$b_x^B = b_x(1 + z) - b_y \tan \theta \quad (2.7b)$$

$$a_y^B = a_y(1 - s) - a_x \tan \varphi \quad (2.7c)$$

$$b_y^B = b_y(1 - s) + b_x \tan \varphi \quad (2.7d)$$

where a and b are the correct reciprocal lattice vectors (see Figure 2.1(b)) and the F and B apexes indicate the measured values.

Along y , the correction for F and B are equal. From the experimental point of view we can take the arithmetic mean between the measured values, so we can make the following substitutions:

$$a_y^F, a_y^B \rightarrow a_y^M = \frac{a_y^F + a_y^B}{2} \quad (2.8a)$$

$$b_y^F, b_y^B \rightarrow b_y^M = \frac{b_y^F + b_y^B}{2} \quad (2.8b)$$

Applying 2.8 into 2.6 and 2.7, and inverting we obtain:

$$a_x = \frac{a_x^F + a_y \tan \theta}{1 - z} \quad (2.9a)$$

$$a_x = \frac{a_x^B - a_y \tan \theta}{1 + z} \quad (2.9b)$$

$$b_x = \frac{b_x^F - b_y \tan \theta}{1 - z} \quad (2.9c)$$

$$b_x = \frac{b_x^B + b_y \tan \theta}{1 + z} \quad (2.9d)$$

$$a_y = \frac{a_y^M + a_x \tan \varphi}{1 - s} \quad (2.9e)$$

$$b_y = \frac{b_y^M - b_x \tan \varphi}{1 - s} \quad (2.9f)$$

With substitutions in 2.9 we obtain the corrected values for reciprocal lattice vectors:

$$a_x = \frac{a_x^F (1 - s) + a_y^M \tan \theta}{(1 - z)(1 - s) - \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10a)$$

$$a_x = \frac{a_x^B (1 - s) - a_y^M \tan \theta}{(1 + z)(1 - s) + \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10b)$$

$$a_y = \frac{a_y^M (1 - z) + a_x^F \tan \varphi}{(1 - z)(1 - s) - \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10c)$$

$$a_y = \frac{a_y^M (1 + z) + a_x^B \tan \varphi}{(1 + z)(1 - s) + \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10d)$$

$$b_x = \frac{b_x^F (1 - s) - b_y^M \tan \theta}{(1 - z)(1 - s) - \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10e)$$

$$b_x = \frac{b_x^B (1 - s) + b_y^M \tan \theta}{(1 + z)(1 - s) + \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10f)$$

$$b_y = \frac{b_y^M (1 - z) - b_x^F \tan \varphi}{(1 - z)(1 - s) - \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10g)$$

$$b_y = \frac{b_y^M (1 + z) - b_x^B \tan \varphi}{(1 + z)(1 - s) + \tan \varphi \tan \theta} \quad (2.10h)$$

By equalizing them two by two we can obtain 4 equations in 4 unknowns. However, a more convenient way to find the solution is consider the equalization of terms with the same denominator.

Considering that:

$$a_x = a \cos \alpha \quad (2.11a)$$

$$a_y = a \sin \alpha \quad (2.11b)$$

$$b_x = b \cos \beta \quad (2.11c)$$

$$b_y = b \sin \beta \quad (2.11d)$$

and (see Figure 2.1(b)):

$$a = Cb \quad (2.12a)$$

$$\alpha + \beta = \pi - \gamma \quad (2.12b)$$

Combining 2.11 with 2.12 and considering the identity $\sin \alpha / \cos \beta = \sin \gamma + \cos \gamma \tan \beta$:

$$a_y = C(b_x \sin \gamma + b_y \cos \gamma) \quad (2.13a)$$

$$b_y = \frac{1}{C}(a_x \sin \gamma + a_y \cos \gamma) \quad (2.13b)$$

Applying 2.13 into 2.10 we obtain:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_y^M - Cb_y^M \cos \gamma & -Cb_x^F \sin \gamma & -a_x^F - Cb_x^F \cos \gamma & -Cb_y^M \sin \gamma \\ a_y^M - Cb_y^M \cos \gamma & Cb_x^B \sin \gamma & a_x^B + Cb_x^B \cos \gamma & -Cb_y^M \sin \gamma \\ Cb_y^M - a_y^M \cos \gamma & -a_x^F \sin \gamma & Cb_x^F + a_x^F \cos \gamma & a_y^M \sin \gamma \\ Cb_y^M - a_y^M \cos \gamma & a_x^B \sin \gamma & -Cb_x^B - a_x^B \cos \gamma & a_y^M \sin \gamma \end{pmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} a_y^M - Cb_x^F \sin \gamma - Cb_y^M \cos \gamma \\ -a_y^M + Cb_x^B \sin \gamma + Cb_y^M \cos \gamma \\ Cb_y^M - a_x^F \sin \gamma - a_y^M \cos \gamma \\ -Cb_y^M + a_x^B \sin \gamma + a_y^M \cos \gamma \end{pmatrix}$$

$$d = (z, s, \tan \varphi, \tan \theta)$$

where

$$Ad = B. \quad (2.14)$$

The solution of 2.14 gives the scaling and shearing factors that can be used as indicated in Tables 2.1 and 2.2.

For a square lattice ($a = b$ and $\gamma = \pi$), 2.13 simplifies to:

$$a_x = b_y \quad (2.15a)$$

$$a_y = b_x \quad (2.15b)$$

And:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_y^M & -b_x^F & -a_x^F & -b_y^M \\ a_y^M & b_x^B & a_x^B & -b_y^M \\ b_y^M & -a_x^F & b_x^F & a_y^M \\ b_y^M & a_x^B & -b_x^B & a_y^M \end{pmatrix}$$

$$B = (a_y^M - b_x^F, b_x^B - a_y^M, b_y^M - a_x^F, a_x^B - b_y^M)$$

In Chapter 3 some applications of this approach are reported.

2.1.3 Experimental setup

The STM images reported in this thesis were measured by using an Omicron UHV room temperature (RT) AFM–STM machine with Ape Research electronics. The bias voltage refers to the sample and the images were recorded in constant current mode. A chemically etched W tip was used as the STM probe. The tip was annealed at 700 K by electron bombardment in UHV to remove the native oxide. The STM data were processed with the software Gwyddion (<http://gwyddion.net>).

2.2 XPS

2.2.1 Technique

Photoelectron spectroscopy (PES), and its X-ray variant X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), are experimental techniques consisting in the detection of an electron emitted from a solid by photoelectric effect, in order to determine its binding energy and wave vector. Photoelectron effect was discovered by Hertz in 1887 and later explained by Einstein in 1905, considering the particle nature of light. Within this model a photon of energy $\hbar\omega$ impinging on a sample is absorbed

and its energy transferred to an electron which is in turn emitted with a kinetic energy given by

$$E_K = \hbar\omega - \phi - E_B \quad (2.16)$$

where ϕ is the work function of the solid and E_B the electron binding energy. From the energy distribution and the wave vector of the electron, through some assumptions, it is possible to obtain the electronic dispersion curve in the solid.

Equation 2.16 can be derived within the so-called *three steps model* [16], in which the photoemission process is divided into three parts: excitation of the electron in the solid, electron transfer toward the surface and propagation of the electron from the surface to the vacuum. A fundamental assumption in the PES theory is the *sudden approximation* in which the response of the system upon the creation of the hole is instantaneous and there are no interactions between the emitted electron and the system itself [17].

The binding energy E_B of an electron in an atom is characteristic of each element. This chemical sensitivity is one of the most striking features of XPS which can be used for the analysis of the elements in a sample. In particular, different types of bond determine the so-called chemical shift [18], that is, the deviation of the binding energy from the free atom value. In this way is possible to distinguish atoms depending on their chemical environment, for instance, non-equivalent atoms within a molecule or elements bonded to different atomic species.

Another important property of photoelectron spectroscopy is related to the electron inelastic mean free path in solids. In the energy range of practical interest for a typical XPS experiment, between 10 and 500 eV, it is less than 10 Å, meaning that only photoelectrons excited within a depth of 10 Å from the surface can leave the sample and be detected, making this technique extremely surface sensitive.

2.2.2 Experimental setup: the SuperESCA beamline

Part of the XPS spectra reported in this thesis have been measured at the SuperESCA beamline at Elettra synchrotron. This beamline (the first one operating at Elettra since 1993) combines high energy resolution with high flux of linearly polarized photons in the 900 eV to 1500 eV energy range, thanks to a prefocusing-monochromator-refocusing scheme. The photoelectrons emitted from the sample are collected with a system of 9 electrostatic lenses and brought to a PHOIBOS hemispherical analyser from SPECS GmbH (150 mm mean radius), which is equipped with a delay line home-made detector [19], specifically designed to allow fast XPS acquisition.

2.3 NEXAFS

2.3.1 Technique

The comprehension of the interaction of molecules with surfaces has been, and continue to be, of fundamental importance in a variety of fields and applications; it is just sufficient to think about catalysis of gasoline and ammonia or the technological advancements in semiconductor materials. Near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) is an experimental technique developed during 1980's to specifically study low-Z molecules (mainly constituted by H, C, N, O and F) adsorbed on surfaces. The main capabilities of this technique are the detection of specific bonds in molecules (*e.g.* C-H, C-C, C=C) and the determination of the bond lengths, but also the orientation of the molecule or functional groups on the surface as well as the orbitals involved in chemisorption processes. Low-Z molecules are particularly suitable to be studied with this technique due to their strong bond directionality which, combined with light polarization of NEXAFS, result in a strong dichroism for angle dependent measurements. These kind of molecules have also a strong dependence of the bond length on its hybridization; this, combined with a large back-scattering cross section of the low-Z atoms, provides clear structure-sensitive resonances in the first 30 eV after the threshold [20].

Experimentally, the X-ray energy is scanned through a specific atomic species threshold and the absorbed X-ray intensity is measured. In particular, as the photon energy is increased from below the absorption threshold of the probed atom, photoelectrons are excited from core levels by the absorbed X-rays. The created holes are then filled by Auger decay (which is dominant in the soft X-ray region over fluorescence). As the photon energy is increased more, a photoemission peak is then observed. The intensity of the emitted primary Auger electrons, however, will follow the absorption cross-section of the atomic shell. In the so-called Auger electron yield (AEY) modality, the recorded intensity of the Auger peak is a direct measure of the X-ray absorption and, due to the small electron escape depth, is an highly surface sensitive technique (~ 1 nm).

As they leave the sample, primary Auger electrons create many scattered secondary electrons which dominate the total electron yield (TEY) intensity. This is the most simple detection modality and consists of collecting electrons of all energies from the sample. The TEY cascade involves several scattering events and originates from an average depth, the electron sampling depth, of few nanometres. Electrons created deeper loose too much energy to overcome the work-function barrier of the sample, thus not contributing to the TEY intensity.

However, this detection technique suffers from the interference of photoemission peaks entering in the measured intensity. In the partial electron yield (PEY) variant, only electrons with a kinetic energy larger than a set threshold value

are detected; by suitably choosing this threshold, the presence of photoemission peaks in the detected kinetic energy window over the spanned energy range can be avoided [20].

The fine structure of NEXAFS arises when the photoelectrons coming from the probed element are excited into unoccupied orbitals, so when the X-ray energy is tuned close to the ionization potential and electrons are excited just few electronvolts above the Fermi level. NEXAFS is element specific because the X-ray absorption edges of different elements have different energies and is sensitive to the bonding environment of the absorbing atom, which results in a chemical shift similar to the case of XPS, but also with a considerably different fine-structure line-shape, thus allowing to achieve a higher sensitivity. Moreover, the major asset of NEXAFS is its polarization dependence. When the electric field of a linearly polarized photon is aligned with the unoccupied orbitals in which electrons are excited, the intensity increases, while when they are orthogonal it is quenched. This allows to determine the orientation of these empty orbitals and thus the orientation of functional groups and simple molecules on the surface. In the simple picture of a diatomic molecule, the empty final states are constituted by Rydberg states below the vacuum energy and a continuum above, as in the case of an isolated atom. In addition, there are unfilled molecular orbitals which, for neutral molecules, typically lies above the vacuum level. However, due to Coulomb electron-hole interactions, the empty orbitals at lower energies are usually pulled down below the vacuum level, between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the vacuum level (typically π^* orbitals) while the others remains above the vacuum level (typically σ^* orbitals) [20].

2.3.2 Experimental setup: the ALOISA beamline

NEXAFS spectra reported in this thesis were taken at the ALOISA beamline at Elettra synchrotron. The spectra were measured in partial electron yield mode by means of a channeltron facing the sample, with an energy resolution of 80 meV [21]. The low-energy secondary electrons have been filtered out by means of a negatively polarized grid placed in front of the sample (230 V for the C edge and 370 V for the N edge). The orientation of the surface with respect to the linear polarization of the synchrotron beam was changed by rotating the sample around the beam axis while keeping a constant grazing angle of 6° . This scattering geometry allows to change the linear polarization of the light from s to p without varying the illuminated area on the sample [22]. The raw data were normalized to the total photon flux and, in the case of spectra taken on the molecular layer, divided by the clean substrate signal.

2.4 XMCD

2.4.1 Technique

X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) is a polarization effect in X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), initially proposed by Schütz and co-workers in 1987 [23], which allows to determine spin and angular momentum order in a sample. The remarkable feature of XAS is the direct coupling of the X-ray electric field to the charge and the X-ray angular momentum to the electron angular momentum and spin. The absorption processes are governed by electric dipole transitions that obey strict selection rules on angular momentum conservation and couple different core shells to specific valence shells. Spin orbit coupling in these final states allows to be sensitive to the electronic spin in the absorption process.

Experimentally, the XMCD measurement technique is equivalent to NEXAFS, but, instead of linearly polarized photons, in order to be sensitive to the angular momentum, circularly polarized light is sent to the sample. Left and right circularly polarized photons possess opposite angular momenta which are transferred to the photoelectron excited from the core shell. The photoelectron then possesses a well defined angular momentum and, in a one-electron picture, one may view the empty valence shell as a detector of this momentum [24, 25].

The X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) absorption intensity is defined as the intensity difference measured with left and right circularly polarized light. Specific sum rules links this intensity to the size of the orbital and spin momenta of the empty valence states [26–28]. Similarly to the case of NEXAFS, angle dependent measurements in magnetic fields can determine the anisotropies of the orbital moment and of the spin density.

In the case of transition metals such as Fe, Co, and Ni, the absorption spectra for XMCD are usually measured at the L-edge, in which the incoming photon excite a $2p$ electron to a $3d$ state [29, 30].

2.4.2 Experimental setup: the BACH beamline

XMCD measurements reported in this thesis have been performed at the BACH beamline at Elettra. The beamline works in the UV-soft x-ray photon energy range (from 35 eV to 1600 eV) with selectable light polarization (linear, circular and elliptical) [31]. The end-station is provided with a hemispherical electron energy analyser Scienta 3000 at 60° from the incident photon beam in the horizontal plane, operating in the the partial electron yield mode.

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Chapter 3

Adsorption of porphyrins on crystal surfaces

3.1 Introduction

The self-assembly of organic monolayers on metal surfaces is a pathway to produce nano-sized metal-organic architectures and patterned surfaces not achievable by conventional methods [1–4].

In porphyrins, the presence of the unsaturated macrocycle brings about great versatility for these chemical systems because of the presence of different positions in which functional groups can be substituted to introduce new properties to the molecule [5, 6].

Moreover, the macrocycle can coordinate with a wide range of metal ions, forming metallo-porphyrins [7]. In this case, the interaction of the metal host at the center of the molecule with the substrate plays a fundamental role in the adsorption behaviour, affecting chemical, electronic and magnetic properties of the system [8–11].

Taking advantage of the flexibility in choosing the substituents, in combination with the presence of active sites of interactions with metals, this kind of molecules can be used to fabricate two-dimensional arrays of metallic centres with nanometric spacing, rendering them suitable candidates as building blocks for novel metal–organic architectures in solid-state chemistry and in molecular engineering [5, 7–10, 12–14] as well as to form patterned surfaces for catalytic, magnetic, optoelectronic, and sensing materials [15–22].

Understanding and controlling the properties of such organic-inorganic interfaces, constitutes a basic step toward the exploitation of new molecular-based devices with controllable and tunable properties [23].

3.2 Self-assembly on metal surfaces: STM of TPP monolayers on Au(111), Ag(111) and Cu(100)

Porphyrin molecules have the ability to self-assembly on crystal surfaces, constituting long-range ordered structures. The periodic arrangement of the molecules and the cell parameters of the formed super-lattice are of great importance in determining the electronic properties of the resulting layer. In fact, the relative position of the molecule with respect to the surface, as well as the relative distance between the molecules themselves, besides being determinant for the molecule-substrate interaction, is strictly related to process such as the metalation and the magnetic exchange coupling.

STM can give precise information on the topology and geometry of the adsorbed porphyrin layers. In the following, STM measurements for a TPP monolayer adsorbed on Au(111), Ag(111) and Cu(100) are reported. All the measurements were performed at RT. In this regime, thermal drift is usually not negligible and its correction is fundamental in order to perform a quantitative measurement. For this reason, the micrograph images were processed by the drift correction algorithm described in Section 2.1.2.

3.2.1 2H-TPP on Ag(111) and MnTPPCL on Au(111)

Figure 3.1(a) reports an STM micrograph at RT of a 2H-5,10,15,20-tetra-phenylporphyrin (2H-TPP) monolayer on Ag(111) obtained after the sublimation of the multilayer at 550 K. The square molecular lattice is aligned with its diagonals parallel to the [110] and [112] substrate symmetry directions. The molecular spacing along these directions suggest a (4x7) periodicity with respect to the substrate lattice. These values are in agreement with RHEED and STM results reported for CoTPP on the same substrate [24]. The square symmetry is the same reported by Di Santo et al. [2] even if Papageorgiou et al. [3] observed the predicted rectangular geometry resulting after the dehydrogenation process (see next section).

For the case of as-deposited molecular monolayer, density functional theory (DFT) calculations predict that the most stable configuration corresponds to a molecule with the phenyl rings tilted with respect to the macrocycle by about 33° at 0 K and 64.5° at 550 K. In this configuration, the adsorption energy of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) at 0 K is calculated to be 2.8 eV [2]. This strong interaction with the Ag surface is reflected also in the fact that the annealing at temperatures higher than 600 K does not promote the sublimation of the first layer, but instead results in the molecule disruption.

On Au(111) the TPP molecules also arrange in a regular lattice. Figures 3.1(b) and 3.1(c) are STM micrographs of a monolayer of MnTPPCL on Au(111). The

Figure 3.1: (a) STM micrograph of 2H-TPP monolayer on Ag(111) at RT. Inset scale bar 4 nm (1 V, 0.03 nA). (a, b) STM micrographs of MnTPP-Cl monolayer on Au(111) at RT. (b) Inset scale bar 20 nm (0.8 V, 0.04 nA). (c) Inset scale bar 5 nm (1.1 V, 0.04 nA).

substrate reconstruction is still visible even after the molecular layer adsorption. The herringbone reconstruction is not modified by the presence of the molecules, as it happens instead, for example, in the case of the missing row reconstruction of Au(110) which is modified by the adsorption of phthalocyanines [25]. Differently to the case of Ag, this indicates that on Au(111) the molecule-substrate interaction is weaker. This point will be further discussed in the next section, concerning the conformational adaptation of 2H-TPP.

3.2.2 NiTPP on Cu(100)

On surfaces with square unit cell, due to their D_{4h} symmetry, TPP molecules arrange in a square lattice. On these surfaces, in the case the molecule super-lattice vectors are not parallel to those of the substrate lattice, there are two equivalent symmetry directions resulting in the formation of two adsorption domains.

Cu has simple cubic crystal structure with a unit lattice of 361.49 pm and thus

Figure 3.2: (a) STM micrograph of NiTPP monolayer on Cu(100). Inset 5 nm (0.2 V, 0.035 nA). (b) 2D FFT of the STM image. (c) IFT after applying a pass filter. The two domains are clearly visible.

its (100) surface has a square unit cell with the same periodicity. Figures 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4 shows a sequence of STM micrographs for a NiTPP monolayer on Cu(100). In Figures 3.2, 3.3, the two different domains are clearly visible. In order to identify them in the real space image (Figures 3.2(c) and 3.3(c)), a 2D pass filter has been applied on the 2D FFT (Figures 3.2(b) and 3.3(b)) of the STM micrograph (Figures 3.2(a) and 3.3(a)). The molecular resolution in Figure 3.4(a) allows to determine the molecule orientation inside the super-lattice.

The comparison of the direction and magnitude of the lattice wave vectors between the clean Cu substrate and the NiTPP layer allows the determination of the molecular adsorption matrix. It is worth noting that thermal drift has a dominant effect on the geometry of the resulting image, as pointed out in Section 2.1; thus its correction is essential for a quantitative analysis.

The two adsorption domains result to be rotated by $\sim 16^\circ$ and the mirror symmetry axes between the two is rotated by 45° with respect to the substrate lattice. The lattice constant of the molecular layer is commensurate with the substrate with a x5 periodicity. The resulting molecular adsorption matrix for a

Figure 3.3: (a) STM micrograph of NiTPP monolayer on Cu(100). Inset 25 nm (0.3 V, 0.1 nA). (b) 2D FFT of the STM image. (c) IFT after applying a pass filter. The patches of the two domains are visible.

Figure 3.4: (a) STM micrograph with molecular resolution of one domain. The molecule orientation inside the domain is visible. Inset 5 nm (0.3 V, 0.05 nA). (b) FFT relative to a single domain. (c) Model for a NiTPP monolayer on Cu(100) showing the two domains.

NiTPP monolayer on Cu(100) is reported in the model of Figure 3.4(c) [[11]]. In particular, the first domain is aligned along the [4,3,0] and [3,-4,0] directions and the second along the [3,4,0] and [4,-3,0] directions.

3.3 Conformational adaptation of 2HTPP monolayer on Au(111)

2H-TPP molecules have been deposited on several metallic substrates, but Au [26–28] and Ag [3, 18, 29–33] are those on which it is possible to obtain a single layer without any modification of the macrocycle. In both cases, when deposited at room temperature (RT) or when the monolayer is obtained after the sublimation of a multilayer in the range $525 \div 580$ K, the XPS analysis shows the presence of two unaffected N 1s peaks, indicating that, in the monolayer, the molecule macrocycle is still protonated. Actually, AuTPP and AgTPP can be synthesized and exist as stable compounds. The fact that the TPP molecule does not metalate on Au and Ag substrates can be explained by the steric hindrance of these atoms, whose ionic radius is larger with respect to atoms such as Fe and Ni, thus not allowing the coordination with the already stable and formed TPP molecule. Moreover, the thermodynamics related to the extraction of an atom from the surface could be unfavourable with respect to the sublimation or disruption of the molecule on the surface.

However, a remarkable effect on the phenyls adsorption geometry was observed on the monolayer (or sub-monolayer) of 2H-TPPs, after annealing above 525 K. On the Ag(111) and Au(111) surfaces, the macrocycle of 2H-TPP deposited at RT has been shown to be adsorbed parallel to the substrate surface, adopting a saddle shape conformation [34], whereas its phenyl legs exhibit a tilt angle of about $45^\circ \div 55^\circ$ with respect to the surface plane [33, 34]. Differently, after annealing above 525 K, a temperature-induced conformational adaptation of the porphyrin molecules on the surface of Ag(111) has been predicted and observed, resulting in the rotation of the phenyl rings parallel to the substrate plane [3, 33].

In the following is presented a study of the electronic and geometric properties of 2H-tetra-phenyl-porphyrins monolayer adsorbed on Au(111) surface. The molecule-surface interaction is studied for a monolayer as-deposited on the surface and after annealing up to 570 K. It will be shown that the annealing process results in a conformational adaptation of the molecule, with the rotation of the phenyl rings towards the surface, similarly to the case of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) [33], and, in addition, with a partial distortion of the macrocycle.

Figure 3.5: N K NEXAFS for 2HTPP multilayer (purple), monolayer as-deposited (blue) and after annealing at 570 K (black) on Au(111) for light polarization parallel (s-polarization, light colour) and perpendicular (p-polarization, dark colour) to the substrate surface. Shaded peaks are the single components resulting from a multi peak fitting procedure; for simplicity only the main components of the π^* region for the p-polarization are shown.

3.3.1 NEXAFS

NEXAFS is an experimental technique able to relate the transitions from the K shell of the probed element to the π^* and σ^* empty orbitals of the molecule. Electron transitions to these states are enhanced when the linear polarization of the impinging photons is parallel to the empty orbitals and are quenched when it is perpendicular. In simple molecules this allows to determine their orientation with respect to the substrate surface plane [35].

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 shows, respectively, the the N K and C K NEXAFS for the 2H-TPP monolayer, before and after annealing at 570 K, and for the multilayer on Au(111), for the light polarization parallel (s-polarization) and normal (p-polarization) to the surface plane.

N K NEXAFS clearly shows that, when the light polarization is normal to

the surface plane, π^* features are enhanced, whereas, when it is parallel, they are completely suppressed. This indicates that the macrocycle, in which the N atoms are located, is parallel with respect to the substrate surface, both for the case of the monolayer and the multilayer. This first result tells us that (i) the molecule macrocycle preserves its parallel orientation after the annealing process and (ii) the molecules in the multilayer are stacked parallel to each other, at least up to a thickness of ~ 6 monolayer (ML). The data fitting indicates a shift towards lower energies for the main π^* features from the multilayer to the monolayer, with a further decrease after the annealing process, as a consequence of the shift of the core level (see Figure 3.8). In particular the first transition at 399.1 eV is shifted by 0.2 eV after the annealing process. Actually, this peak does not completely vanish for s-polarization, as can be seen by the presence of a bulge in the multilayer and the monolayer as-deposited, while it disappears after the annealing. This feature is related to the pyrrolic nitrogen and it will be discussed later in the XPS section 3.3.2.

The situation is quite different in the case of the C threshold. As reported in [36], C K NEXAFS spectrum of TPP molecule is almost the superposition of the macrocycle and the phenyl (benzene) spectra. The most relevant feature related to the phenyl π^* absorption component is the peak at ~ 285.1 eV, whereas the first π^* absorption peak at ~ 284.2 eV is due to the macrocycle.

For both the multilayer and the monolayer, the macrocycle π^* peaks follow the same behaviour of the N K edge NEXAFS, *i.e.* the feature is enhanced for out-of-plane polarization and is completely suppressed for in-plane polarization, again confirming that the macrocycle is adsorbed parallel to the substrate surface.

For the multilayer, applying the formula by Stöhr [35], the dichroic signal for the peak at ~ 285.1 eV indicates that the phenyl rings are rotated by an average angle of $\sim 56.3^\circ$ with respect to the macrocycle. This T-shaped geometry is expected, considering that in gas-phase and in solution the meso-substituent tends to align to an average angle in the range $50 \div 80^\circ$, due to the steric interaction between the hydrogens atoms [37].

In the case of the monolayer as-deposited there is an increase in the dichroism of the phenyl moiety component with respect to the multilayer, indicating a rotation of the phenyl rings towards the surface, with an average aryl angle of $\sim 34.1^\circ$; this effect is related to the interaction between the substrate and the π orbitals of the phenyl moieties [38].

After the annealing process this peak is almost completely suppressed for s-polarization, suggesting that in this case the phenyl rings lies flat on the surface. This behaviour is quite exceptional considering that the rotation of the phenyl rings is inhibited by the steric interaction between the hydrogen atoms in the molecule and they are expected to be rotated with respect to the macrocycle [16–19, 30, 39].

The reaction can be explained under the assumption that the molecules un-

Figure 3.6: C K NEXAFS for 2HTPP multilayer (purple), monolayer as-deposited (blue) and after annealing at 570 K (black) on Au(111) for light polarization parallel (s-polarization, dark colour) and perpendicular (p-polarization, light colour) to the substrate surface. Shaded peaks are the single components resulting from a multi peak fitting procedure; for simplicity only the main components of the π^* region for the p-polarization are shown.

Figure 3.7: C K NEXAFS for a 2HTPP monolayer on Au(111) as-deposited (blue) and after annealing at 470 K (orange), 520 K (red) and 570 K (black) for light polarization parallel (s-polarization, thicker lines) and perpendicular (p-polarization, thinner lines) to the substrate surface.

dergo a dehydrogenation reaction of both benzene rings and external part of the macrocycle, ending up with the formation of four new aryl-aryl carbon bonds. In this way, with the rotation of the benzene moieties, the molecule becomes flat and, therefore, reduces the distance from the substrate, making new and stronger bonds between their molecular π orbitals (both from phenyls and macrocycle) and the substrate bands. The details of this configuration can be described within the density functional theory (DFT) formalism [33].

As will be discussed in the next chapter (section 4.4), the study of a submonolayer of CoTPP evaporated on Ag(111) demonstrated that the molecule increases the number of bonds and reaches a more stable energetic configuration via this mechanism. The Co at the centre of the macrocycle, like other 3d metals (Fe, Ni, Mn, Cu), has a strong interaction with the substrate via the perpendicular d_{z^2} orbital, inducing the molecule to form bonds with the π orbitals. Indeed, after annealing up to 600 K, the CoTPP molecule does not change the orientation of the phenyl rings, that remain rotated by approximately 40° with respect to the macrocycle, which instead is parallel to the substrate surface [40]. A strong interaction with the substrate prevents this reconfiguration of the molecule; otherwise, when the interaction is weaker, like in the case of Zn, the rotation of the phenyl rings of ZnTPP is allowed [41] as for the case of the 2H-TTP molecule.

To better understand the thermodynamics of the reaction, the annealing process

Figure 3.8: Experimental data (dots) and curve fitting (solid) of N 1s XPS for 2HTPP multilayer (purple), monolayer as-deposited (blue) and after annealing at 570 K (black) on Au(111). Peak positions and intensities are marked by vertical lines.

has been performed in different steps at increasing temperature (470 K, 520 K and 570 K). Figure 3.7 shows the evolution of C K edge NEXAFS with the annealing temperature. It is evident the decreasing of the phenyl components for the polarization normal to the surface and, at the same time, their increasing for the other polarization. In particular, can be noted that, after a small reduction with the first annealing, there is a marked step between 470 ÷ 520 K, indicating that the reaction occurs mainly in this range, and it is completed at 570 K.

All the measurement were made at low temperature (~ 170 K), after the annealing processes, to reduce the radiation damage of the molecular film. Moreover, as a consequence of the weak interaction of the molecule with the substrate, the cooling process is also needed in order to prevent the molecular film sublimation.

3.3.2 XPS

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements on the Nitrogen 1s core level energy region, either done on 2H-TTP multilayer in solid state [2, 17, 42], either on the same molecular species in gas-phase [43], highlights the typical feature of the macrocycle, in which the existence of two components, separated by ~ 2 eV, can be detected (iminic and pyrrolic).

Figure 3.9: Experimental data (dots) and curve fitting (solid) of C 1s core level XPS for 2HTPP multilayer (purple), monolayer as-deposited (blue) and after annealing at 570 K (black) on Au(111). Peak positions and intensities are marked by vertical lines.

In Figure 3.8 the XPS spectrum for N 1s core level for 2H-TPP on Au(111) is reported. The component at higher binding energy (BE) corresponds to the pyrrolic N atom (=NH) while the iminic N component is shifted at lower binding energy. In the case of the multilayer they are positioned at 399.69 eV and 397.61 eV respectively, with a relative distance of 2.08 eV.

In the case of C 1s, different components are expected which account for the different species inside the molecule [44]. However since the chemical shift between these components is small compared with the energy blurring due to the screening of the molecular multilayer, the C 1s core level spectrum shows, in this case, not more than a single peak located at 284.4 eV (Figure 3.9).

Tuning the evaporation conditions it is possible to evaporate almost exactly 1 ML of 2HTPP, and the coverage can be determined by measuring the intensity ratio between the C 1s core level and the Au of the substrate.

In the monolayer as-deposited both N peaks undergo a rigid shift of 0.43 eV towards lower binding energies (BE of 399.26 eV for pyrrolic and 397.18 eV for iminic N). This is attributed to the increased screening effect and to changes in the surface dipole due to the interaction with the substrate, arising from the closer vicinity to the surface. In this case, for the two N components both the shape and intensity remain the same, indicating that the macrocycle is still protonated and the molecule does not metalate, as it happens in the case of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) [33]. It can be noted that the intensities of the two peaks are slightly different, with a reduction in area of the iminic peak of $\sim 15\%$ with respect to the pyrrolic one: this can be ascribed to a photoelectron diffraction effect as reported in [33]. In the C 1s XPS of the monolayer there is an overall shift of the spectra towards lower BE. In this case three components can be resolved, even if are not clearly assignable to the different carbon atoms of the molecule.

After annealing at 570 K, the pyrrolic component does not change its position (399.26 eV), while the iminic N peak shifts at higher binding energy by 0.23 eV (BE=397.41 eV). The opposite shift is visible in the N K NEXAFS for the first absorption peak, (Figure 3.5) which corresponds to the transition from the iminic Nitrogen 1s core level to the π^* empty molecular orbitals. In the same figure, it can be seen that, for the case of the multilayer and the monolayer as-deposited, the first iminic peak is actually still visible in s-polarization, while it is completely suppressed after the annealing process. Considering that the molecule macrocycle is completely parallel to the surface, this indicates that the macrocycle is adopting a saddle shape conformation [34], while it becomes more planar after the annealing process. At the same time, the main component of the C 1s orbital, shifts toward lower binding energy as a consequence of the rotation of the phenyl rings parallel to the substrate surface, with a change in the peak line-shape that becomes similar to that of a monolayer of Pc on Ag(111) [45].

The hypothesis of 2H-TPP modification is supported by recent analyses [3, 46],

among which the most complete was proposed by Papageorgiou et al. [3], who observed all the predicted dehydrogenation configurations on Ag(111) surface through STM.

In the case of Au(111), substrate reconstruction must be explicitly taken into account, as well as interactions due to charge-transfer processes. These additional interactions clearly affect the rotation of the phenyl rings towards the surface, in order to increase the interaction between the s-p bands of Au and the p orbitals of the carbon atoms.

A similar behaviour was observed, for example, in the case of cyclohexaphenylene on Cu(111) in which the dehydrogenation occurs at 470 K [47], or the case of porphyrins on Cu(110) in which the reaction generates highly oriented one-dimensional organometallic macromolecular wires [46].

3.3.3 Experimental

The data was collected at ALOISA beamline at Elettra Synchrotron radiation facility. The experiments were performed in UHV with a base pressure of 10^{-10} mbar. Commercial 2H-TPP molecules were sublimated, after degassing, on Au(111) by using a boron nitride crucible held at 570 K. The Au(111) surface was prepared by Ar ion sputtering at 1.5 keV and annealing at 770 K. The absence of contaminants were checked by means of X-ray photoemission spectroscopy.

NEXAFS spectra were taken in partial electron yield mode by means of a channeltron facing the sample, while scanning the photon energy across the C and N K-edge with an energy resolution of 80 meV [48]. The low-energy secondary electrons have been filtered out by means of a negatively polarized grid (230 V for the carbon edge and 370 V for the nitrogen edge) placed in front of the sample. The orientation of the surface with respect to the linear polarization of the synchrotron beam was changed by rotating the sample around the beam axis while keeping a constant grazing angle of 6° . This scattering geometry allows changing the linear polarization of the light from s ($\theta = 0^\circ$) to p-polarization ($\theta = 84^\circ$) geometry without variation of the illuminated area on the sample [49]. The raw data were normalized to the total photon flux. The XPS data were collected by means of a hemispherical electron energy analyser with a resolution of 100 meV. The binding energy was obtained by setting the Fermi level of Au(111) at 0 eV.

3.4 Conformational adaptation: the case of 2HTPP on Ag(111)

The sublimation of a 2H-TPP multilayer in the temperature range of $525 \div 600$ K is the most common way to produce a self-assembled monolayer on Ag(111) [17–

Figure 3.10: N K NEXAFS for 2HTPP multilayer (purple) and monolayer (blue) obtained by the sublimation of the multilayer after annealing at 570 K on Ag(111), for light polarization parallel (s-polarization, light colour) and perpendicular (p-polarization, dark colour) to the substrate surface.

[19, 24, 39]. Figure 3.10 and 3.11 shows the NEXAFS at the nitrogen and carbon K threshold respectively, for both the 2H-TPP multilayer and monolayer on Ag(111). As discussed for Au(111) the absorption spectra clearly show the rotation of the phenyl rings upon annealing at 525 K.

By using DFT calculations, Di Santo et al. [50] explain this behaviour with the formation of a new molecule in which the phenyl rings are connected to the macrocycle through new carbon–carbon bonds. The hypothesis of 2H-TPP modification is supported by several recent analyses [3, 46], among which the most complete was by Papageorgiou et al. [3], who observed all the predicted dehydrogenation configurations through STM.

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Figure 3.11: C K NEXAFS for 2HTPP multilayer (purple) and monolayer (blue) obtained by the sublimation of the multilayer after annealing at 570 K on Ag(111), for light polarization parallel (s-polarization, light colour) and perpendicular (p-polarization, dark colour) to the substrate surface.

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Chapter 4

Metalation of tetra-phenyl-porphyrins

4.1 Introduction

In-situ metalation of porphyrin molecules in UHV is of great interest for the production of metal-organic systems in a controlled environment. These complexes, the so-called metallo-porphyrins, are typically constituted by a metal ion complexed to the four nitrogen atoms in the center of the conjugated macrocycle. These molecules play a key role in several oxidative catalytic processes, including biological systems. Iron-porphyrins, for example, may undergo reversible redox reactions and are very sensitive toward oxidation. Generally, the inclusion of metal atoms in porphyrin molecules is obtained via chemical reaction in solution, and typically this requires a ligand coordinated to the metal atom in order to reduce its reactivity and prevent oxidation. The possibility to produce *in-situ* stable pure metallo-porphyrins without any ligand and to characterize them is an intriguing challenge of fundamental interest.

Furthermore, the capability of this type of molecules to bind various metal ions opens the discussion on the processes involved in the metalation as well as on how the presence of this central metal atom modifies the interaction with the substrate. The achievement of a complete metalation can be regarded as a test case for successful preparation of well-defined and controlled arrays of molecular-based magnets.

Several metals can be efficiently coordinated to 2H-TPP adsorbed on Ag(111) and Au(111) by *in-situ* metal evaporation: Fe [1–3], Co [4, 5], Ni [6], Zn [7], Ce [8], Mn and Rh [[1]] can be easily inserted in the macrocycle to form metallo-porphyrins. The metals can be coordinated either by direct evaporation on the 2H-TPP monolayer or multilayer, or by deposition of metal ad-atoms on the

substrate before the molecules evaporation.

Recently it was shown that on some reactive substrates with a small ionic radius, like the first row *3d* transition metals, the 2H-TPP monolayer metalates simply by picking-up substrate atoms or ad-atoms; this happens on Fe and Ni [9], Cu [10–14] or Al [[12]] (*2p* metal) substrates. In the case of Ni and Fe, experimental results and DFT calculations demonstrate that the molecules metalate at room temperature by incorporating a surface metal ad-atom when a monolayer is deposited on these substrates, while for the case of Cu an annealing to 420 K is required to complete the metalation [12].

Finally, given the difficulty in evaporating some heavy metals (such as Rh, W, Ir or Ru), a useful procedure to metalate the 2H-TPP in UHV has been shown by Papageorgiou et al. [15]. They demonstrated the formation of Ru(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (RuTPP) on Ag(111) after the exposure of 2H-TPP to the carbonyl precursor molecules $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$ containing the metal, followed by a thermal treatment to complete the reaction.

Photoemission spectroscopy is extremely sensitive to the redox-reaction occurring at the macrocycle which leads to the metalation process. The evidence of the metal coordination comes from the changes of the N 1s XPS spectrum of the porphyrin when a metal ion is bound at the centre of the macrocycle. In particular, the spectrum of the 2H-TPP has two easily resolved components because of the two N species: the one at higher binding energy is assigned to the two pyrrolic N atoms (-NH-), while the lower BE peak corresponds to the two iminic ones (-N=); in the metallo-porphyrin, instead, the four N atoms are equivalent, and just one peak is expected.

4.2 Metal evaporation in UHV

Recently, it was demonstrated that, by metal evaporation in UHV, metal ions can be incorporated into adsorbed free-base tetrapyrrole molecules, like porphyrins or phthalocyanines. This metalation process is a redox reaction resulting in the oxidation of the metal and a reduction of the porphyrin ligand. With this method it is possible to metalate the free-base porphyrins, both in the cases of monolayer and multilayer, and various metals can be coordinated to the center of the macrocycle [1–8]

Potentially, this method can be employed to synthesize those metallo-porphyrins whose extreme reactivity prevents its existence as a free compound and thus does not allow a direct evaporation. The unfavourable oxidation states of the metal ion, although needed for the existence of such compounds, can be stabilized by the presence of a surface: the interaction with the underlying substrate, acting as an electron donor, may allow their existence.

Some chemically synthesized metallo-porphyrins, such as those containing Fe, Mn, Au and Rh metal ions, are stabilized as free molecules by the coordination of the metal ion to a ligand, such as Cl or a functional group, to reduce its reactivity and prevent oxidation. On the other hand, some of these molecules could also be produced on a surface by evaporating the metal ions into the free-base porphyrins, without the need of a stabilizing ligand.

Recently, it was shown that pure Fe(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (Fe-TPP) can be produced by *in-situ* metalation of free-base 2H-TPP monolayers with Fe atoms deposited by electron beam evaporation in UHV [3]. STM micrographs with sub-molecular resolution showed the appearance of intra-molecular protrusions after Fe evaporation as the evidence of the TPP metalation. Similar experiments have been performed for Co and Ce [8]. Moreover, photoemission studies have demonstrated metalation of 2H-TPP by Fe, Zn, and Co by monitoring the core level of the N 1s and the metal ion [1, 4, 7]. Similarly, metalation experiments were also performed on free-base phthalocyanines [16].

In the following the metalation of 2H-TPP monolayer and multilayer on Ag(111) with Mn, Rh and Fe is reported.

4.2.1 Mn-TPP and Rh-TPP on Ag(111)

As already mentioned, the XPS spectra at the N 1s core-level provides the evidence of the metalation process and the evolution of the metal coordination reaction can be directly followed with this technique. In Figure 4.1, the sequence of the N 1s line shape changes during Mn evaporation is shown. The two distinct components of the pristine 2H-TPP multilayer spectrum (red) indicate the presence of the intact macrocycle of the free base molecule, with the iminic N peak at ~ 398 eV and the pyrrolic at ~ 400 eV. The two inequivalent nitrogen components are reduced to a single component at 398.5 eV while the Mn atoms are evaporated and react with the deposited porphyrin multilayer (blue and black spectra in the same Figure). The N 1s spectrum changes toward a single peak configuration, which corresponds to four equivalent nitrogen atoms in the macrocycle, all unprotonated and coordinated with the same Mn atom.

As it is shown in Figure 4.1, the metalation of the multilayer film is almost complete; the presence of a small shoulder at lower energy confirms that not all of the molecules have been metalated.

The normalized peak areas for the iminic and pyrrolic components in the pristine 2H-TPP, show clearly an uneven proportion. This can be explained with a photoelectron diffraction effect: in the off-normal experimental geometry at which electrons are collected, the ordering of the molecular layers should enhance the photoelectron diffraction modulation.

A similar experiment has been performed by evaporating Rh on 2H-TPP both

Figure 4.1: N 1s core level XPS for a 2H-TPP multilayer on Ag(111) during Mn evaporation. As deposited 2H-TPP multilayer (red) shows the iminic (~ 398 eV) and pyrrolic (~ 400 eV) components of the free base molecule. During the Mn evaporation (blue and black) a new peak appears at 398.5 eV, which corresponds to the metalated molecule.

Figure 4.2: Evolution of the N 1s core level XPS for a 2H-TPP monolayer (top) and multilayer (bottom) on Ag(111) for subsequent Rh evaporation steps. As deposited 2H-TPP (red) shows the iminic and pyrrolic components (~ 398 eV and ~ 400 eV respectively) of the empty molecules, in both cases. During the Rh evaporation (colors for multilayer case) the metalated Rh-TPP peak appears at 398.85 eV in the case of multilayer and 398.65 eV for the monolayer. This shift is due to the electron transfer and the better screening effect of the substrate in the case of the monolayer.

Figure 4.3: Evolution of the N 1s core level XPS for a 2H-TPP multilayer on Ag(111) at different Fe evaporation steps. As deposited 2H-TPP (top) is constituted by the iminic (~ 397.9 eV, light purple) and pyrrolic (~ 399.9 eV, dark purple) components. During the Fe evaporation the peak corresponding to the N-Fe bond (green) appears at 398.6 eV. The coloured peaks are the single components resulting from a multi-peak fitting procedure.

in the case of a monolayer and a multilayer (Figure 4.2). The monolayer is defined as the saturated layer obtained by the multilayer desorption. The monolayer XPS peaks positions rigidly shift toward lower binding energy by 0.2 eV with respect to the multilayer case; this is related to the formation of a surface dipole, in the case of the monolayer, by electrons being transferred from the substrate and to the better screening of the core-hole due to the underlying metal. The metalated Rh-TPP component appears at 398.85 eV for the multilayer and 398.65 eV for the monolayer. Moreover, it can be noted that there is a minor photoelectron diffraction effect for the monolayer with respect to the multilayer in this adsorption geometry.

The metalation procedure has led to an almost fully metalated monolayer and multilayer, as shown by the single peak of the N 1s spectrum (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.4: N 1s core level XPS for a 2H-TPP monolayer on Ag(111) during Fe evaporation. In pristine 2H-TPP (top) are visible the iminic (~ 397.7 eV, light blue) and pyrrolic (~ 399.7 eV, dark blue) components. The peak corresponding to the N-Fe bond (green) is located at 398.4 eV; its asymmetry, typical of a metallic system, can be ascribed to a strong interaction with the substrate. In this case the peak positions are shifted by 0.2 eV towards lower binding energies with respect to the multilayer. In the last step (30 s) the metalation is complete as can be seen from the presence of a single peak. The coloured peaks are the single components resulting from a multi-peak fit.

4.2.2 Fe-TPP on Ag(111)

In some cases the metal atom in metallo-porphyrins can bring about a magnetic moment, which makes these molecules very interesting from the point of view of their magnetic properties. In chemically synthesized Fe porphyrin, the metal ion is stabilized with a Cl atom to prevent its oxidation, and thus, as it happens for Mn, it is not possible to have a free stable Fe-TPP. The presence of these ligands can affect the electronic and magnetic properties of these molecules in unpredictable ways; the ability to obtain metallic magnetic porphyrins without any ligand, through metal evaporation in UHV, is of great importance in this sense.

In the following, the photoemission and absorption experimental results for the Fe metalation of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) are reported.

Figure 4.3 shows the XPS N 1s core-level line shape changes during Fe evaporation, for a 2H-TPP multilayer on Ag(111). As in the previous case, the two components are related to the two different nitrogen species of the TPP molecule and the small disproportion between the two can be explained with a photoelectron diffraction effect. Curve fitting of the core levels indicates a BE of 399.9 eV for the pyrrolic peak and 397.9 eV for the iminic one, while the peak corresponding to the N-Fe bond is located at 398.6 eV. Moreover, in this case, it can be clearly seen that the pyrrolic peak is broader than the iminic. It is not straightforward to assert that the two N species have a different core-hole lifetime, that should be related to very distinct de-excitation mechanisms. On the other hand, the presence of H atoms bounded to the pyrrolic N atoms, introduces phonon modes related to the N-H bond vibrations [17]. These are expected to result in a broadening of the pyrrolic peak, because of the occurrence of a Franck-Condon effect in the photoemission process, which can be taken into account by a Gaussian broadening of the core-level line-shape.

The monolayer, as seen in the previous chapter, can be obtained by sublimating the multilayer at ~ 550 K. The XPS peak positions in the monolayer (Figure 4.4) rigidly shift toward lower binding energy by 0.2 eV with respect to the multilayer case, due to electron transfer from the substrate and the formation of a surface dipole, with an increased screening due to the underlying metal. In this case the N peaks show a degree of asymmetry, as in the case of metallic systems, which can be explained by a strong interaction of the molecule with the substrate, which is emphasized by the presence of the Fe atoms. In section 4.4, the effects resulting from the presence of the metal atom will be extensively investigated.

The adsorption geometry of 2H-TPP deposited on Ag(111) in the monolayer and multilayer cases can be determined with NEXAFS by investigating the dependence from the linear polarization of the light on the electronic transitions from core levels to empty states. From the comparison between the spectra taken with the light polarization parallel ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and perpendicular ($\theta = 84^\circ$) to the surface,

Figure 4.5: NEXAFS spectra at the N K threshold for 2H-TPP multilayer (purple) and monolayer (blue) on Ag(111) before (a, c) and after (b, d) Fe evaporation. The spectra are taken in linear s-polarization ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and in p-polarization ($\theta = 84^\circ$). In the case of metalated molecule (b, d) is visible the convergence to one single peak of the iminic and pyrrolic components.

Figure 4.6: NEXAFS spectra at the C K threshold for 2H-TPP multilayer (purple) and monolayer (blue) on Ag(111) before (a, c) and after (b, d) Fe evaporation. The spectra are taken in linear s-polarization ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and in p-polarization ($\theta = 84^\circ$). In the multilayer case the presence of the absorption peak in s-polarization is due to the rotation of the phenyl rings, which remains rotated also after the metalation.

it is possible to extract the information about the geometry of the system. As in the case of 2H-TPP on Au(111) in the previous chapter, the comparison between NEXAFS and XPS is able to clarify the electronic structure of the molecular film.

Figure 4.5 shows the N K-edge NEXAFS spectrum of the 2H-TPP monolayer and multilayer, before and after Fe evaporation. The multilayer spectrum is similar to the 2H-TPP gas-phase spectrum, indicating that the interaction between the molecules is weak. In this case, the complete quenching of the π^* states in s-polarization, indicates a flat adsorption of the macrocycle. The Fe atom coordination at the center of the porphyrin macrocycle, is confirmed by the N K edge absorption spectra: the first two π^* peaks of the 2H-TPP NEXAFS spectrum converge to a single peak located at a photon energy of 398.6 eV. This can be observed also for the monolayer, even if in this case the absorption thresholds, both in the case of free and metalated molecule, occurs at lower photon energies. In this case the first π^* absorption peak, related to the iminic transition, appears at 397.7 eV, equal to the binding energy of the N 1s iminic component measured in photoemission. The correspondence with the photoemission BE is found also for the first π^* transition in the metalated case. Again, this agrees with a metal-like behaviour of the monolayer as shown by core level XPS.

The geometry assumed by the whole molecule, in particular by the phenyl rings with respect to the macrocycle, can be determined by the analysis of the absorption spectra at the C K edge (Figure 4.6).

As seen in the previous chapter, the first structure at ~ 284 eV is assigned to the macrocycle, while the absorption peak at ~ 285 eV is mainly due to the π^* states located in the phenyl rings [18]. As in the case of the N K threshold, the first π^* transition due to the macrocycle disappears in s-polarization, indicating again that the macrocycle lies flat with respect to the substrate surface plane, while the phenyl peak is still present, thus indicating a non-flat orientation of the meso-substituent rings. In the multilayer, the intermolecular interactions are mainly due to the weak Van der Waals forces and, therefore, the phenyl rings have an orientation similar to the molecules in gas phase, in which they tend to stay at $\sim 70 \div 80^\circ$ with respect to the macrocycle, as a consequence of the hydrogen steric interactions.

On the contrary, the monolayer showed a flat molecular adsorption geometry with a planar conformation for the phenyl groups, as clearly seen from the suppression of all the π^* peaks in the N K and C K NEXAFS s-polarization spectra.

The interface adsorption geometry and the multilayer molecular orientation is directly affected by the metalation process, and a distortion of the macrocycle with a change in the electronic structure may occur. In the case of C K NEXAFS (Figure 4.6), the Fe coordination does not affect the orientation of the macrocycle carbon atoms, as can be seen by the complete quenching of the absorption peak in s-polarization, indicating that the macrocycle is flat as in the case of the empty 2H-TPP. For the N absorption spectra (Figure 4.5), instead, the peak at 398.6 eV is

not completely quenched when the polarization is in the surface plan. The presence of this feature only in the N spectrum suggests that in the Fe-TPP multilayer, the four nitrogen atoms slightly change their orientation, indicating a possible distortion of the N positions, due to the Fe coordination.

The features at photon energies higher than 400 eV are related to the macrocycle, and their changes after the metal evaporation are associated with the metal coordination; the resulting line-shape resemble that of Ni(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin (NiTPP) [19], further confirming the metalation of the molecule.

As pointed out by Di Santo et al. [2], in the monolayer case, while the presence of the metallic center has a minor effect on the macrocycle conformation, the adsorption geometry and the flat orientation of the phenyl rings reduces the degrees of freedom of the metalation process. On the basis of both experimental and theoretical data, the monolayer metalation process has been explained with the diffusion of the metal at the reaction site [1, 20–22] driven by motion onto the substrate surface; however, this model seems inadequate for flat and compact phthalocyanine [16] and 2H-TPP monolayer, covering the whole substrate, thus indicating that, instead, an ad-atom hopping could be responsible for the metalation process.

4.3 Metal atom picking-up from the substrate

Recently, self-metalation of different porphyrin molecules (proto-porphyrin [23], diphenyl porphyrin [10], octa-ethyl porphyrin [24], and 2H-TPP [12]) has been achieved by depositing metal-free molecules on copper surfaces: an atom from the substrate is picked up and coordinates with the molecule macrocycle, forming a metallo-porphyrin.

Except for the case of the proto-porphyrins on Cu(110) [23], these systems need to be annealed above 380 K to complete the redox reaction. This kind of metalation is a consequence of different processes: the dehydrogenation of the macrocycle, the modification of the chemical bondings of the metal atom and the formation of the new bonds with the macrocycle. The temperature at which the metalation occurs, if any, is determined by the energy barrier of these reactions. This indicates that the interface interaction and, in particular, the interplay between the geometric and the electronic structures of the molecule (adsorption geometry, molecular conformation, charge and spin states) are extremely critical in determining the metalation process.

In the following, are reported the results related to the self-metalation of 2H-TPP monolayers on Fe(110) and Al(111), with the formation of Fe-TPP and Al-TPP respectively. The investigations of different metal-organic interfaces and of their interactions is of extreme importance, especially when changes in the

Figure 4.7: N 1s XPS for 2H-TTP monolayer on Au(111) (top, yellow), Ag(111) (middle, blue) and Fe(110) (bottom, red). The presence of two peak for the molecule on Ag(111) and Au(111) indicates it is still protonated. The single peak in the case of Fe indicates that the molecules self-metalate once adsorbed on the surface and all the N atoms are equivalently coordinated to the metal atom.

adsorbed layer can lead to the formation of new molecular species [10, 11, 25] or to a drastic change in molecular geometry, as it is reported here in the case of 2H-TTP/Al(111).

4.3.1 The case of Fe(110)

In this experiment 1 ML of 2H-TTP molecules has been deposited on Fe(110)/Cu(110) at room temperature. In Figure 4.7 are reported the XPS spectra of N 1s core-level, in comparison to a monolayer of 2H-TTP on Ag(111) and on Au(111).

While in the case of Au(111) and Ag(111) the N 1s XPS spectra of a 2H-TTP monolayer show two distinct components correspondent to the iminic and pyrrolic species, in the case Fe(110) just a single peak appears at ~ 398.5 eV. This is the fingerprint of the molecule metalation and the formation of Fe-TTP, in which the four N atoms are equivalent and coordinated with the metal atom. The samples were checked for radiation damages and several spectra were recorded in different

Figure 4.8: NEXAFS at N K-edge for a 2H-TPP monolayer on Fe(110) for p (dark colour) and s (light colour) light polarization. The small peak in s-polarization indicates that the molecule macrocycle is almost parallel to the surface, with a slight distortion due to the presence of the metal atom.

Figure 4.9: C K-edge NEXAFS for a 2H-TPP monolayer deposited on Fe(110) for p (dark colour) and s (light colour) polarizations. The absence of the peak at 284 eV in s-polarization indicates the flat adsorption of the macrocycle, while the dichroism of the second absorption peak at 285 eV indicates that, after the metalation, the phenyl rings are still rotated with respect to the surface by $\sim 30^\circ$.

positions in order to minimize the effect of the light beam. The spectra have been measured both for the monolayer as-deposited and obtained after the sublimation of the multilayer. The multilayer shows the presence of the two N peaks indicating that, as it can be expected, just the molecules of the first molecular layer pick up an atom from the substrate, while the other layers do not metalate. This system will be further investigated in the case of the double layer of TPP in chapter 5.

NEXAFS gives information on the adsorption geometry of the molecules on the substrate. Figure 4.15 shows the N K-edge NEXAFS spectra of the 2H-TPP monolayer deposited on Fe(110), for p-polarization (light polarization close to the surface normal) and s-polarization (polarization in the surface plane). These spectra are similar to those of porphyrin molecules adsorbed on other metal substrates, with Ni and Fe in the macrocycle [26, 27], further indicating the metalation of 2H-TPP.

The macrocycle is almost parallel to the surface plane since the π^* resonances are almost completely suppressed in s-polarization: however, a small peak is still visible, indicating a slight distortion of the macrocycle. The spectra indicate a flat adsorption geometry of the macrocycle with a saddle shape configuration and a distortion angle of the pyrrole rings of about 18° .

C K edge NEXAFS for a 2H-TPP monolayer on Fe(110) is reported in Figure 4.9. The first feature at lower binding energy (~ 284 eV), correspondent to the transitions to the π^* states of the macrocycle, is completely suppressed for s-polarization, again indicating that the macrocycle is parallel to the surface plane. The most intense peak at ~ 285 eV mainly belongs to the excitation into π^* states of phenyl rings [28]. The dichroism, according to the Stöhr formula [29], indicates an average angle between the phenyl rings and the surface plane close to $\sim 30^\circ$.

A similar metalation reaction was observed on Cu(110), after annealing above 380 K [10, 24] and at room temperature [23]. More recently, new experimental evidence of metalation of 2H-TPP on Cu(111) was provided by Diller et al. [12], but just after annealing at about 420 K, which is probably related to the room temperature adsorption conformation of 2H-TPP, as suggested by Buchner and co-workers [30].

According to calculations [20] and experimental [6] evidence, adding a Ni ion in the macrocycle should require annealing above 520 K, while for Fe ions, the reaction may happen also at room temperature. Despite this, the presence of the metallic substrate plays a fundamental role: the chemical potential of the metal atom at the surface is considerably lower compared to the isolated atom case, while molecular rearrangements, in order to include the atom, will have to compete with van der Waals forces. Goldoni et al. [9] provided DFT calculations in the case of 2H-TPP metalation on Ni(111). Their results indicate that the inclusion of Ni ad-atoms is thermodynamically favoured, with a correspondent energy gain of 0.89 eV. On the other hand, the creation of a Ni vacancy by the 2H-TPP molecule is unfavoured, with an energy loss of 0.69 eV, suggesting that this process could be an intermediate step of the whole reaction, which could have a lower overall reaction barrier.

It is worth noting that, due to the presence of the phenyl substituents, the distance of the macrocycle from the substrate is between $2.5 \div 5$ Å depending on the rotation of the phenyl rings and the distortion of the macrocycle [31, 32]. Even considering this distance, the metalation occurs on the Fe(110) surface; as seen in the previous chapter, this does not happens on all substrates, such as Au(111) and Ag(111).

Figure 4.10: N 1s XPS of 2H-TPP monolayer (bottom, blue) and multilayer (top, purple) on Al(111) at 300 K. The broad single peak in the case of the monolayer suggests the self metalation of the molecule, even if some other features are present. The further molecule evaporation results in the appearance of the two N component of the free base multilayer.

4.3.2 The case of Al(111)

2H-TPP on Al(111)

We have seen that metallo-porphyrins can be produced on the surface of metals in UHV by metal evaporation or by self-metalation of the molecules, obtaining some metal complexes which can not be synthesized with other methods. In section 4.4 will be presented some important aspects of the presence of the metal ion inside the molecule and how this affects its chemical and physical properties. On the other hand, the metalation process itself, occurring at the surface, can modify substantially the configuration of the molecule and its absorption geometry. The self-metalation of 2H-TPP on Al(111) is one of these cases.

We have started with the evaporation of ~ 1 ML of 2H-TPP on Al(111) at RT (Figure 4.10). The fingerprint of the metalation process, as seen previously, is the absence of the two N component in the N 1s XPS spectrum. In this case, the presence of a single peak indicates that the molecule macrocycle is not more empty, even if it has a broad and irregular shape and the shoulder at lower binding energies is present. A further evaporation of porphyrin molecules results in the appearance of the two components, correspondent to the iminic and pyrrolic N, in the XPS spectrum, indicating the intact multilayer of 2H-TPP.

In order to have a better insight into the thermodynamics of the metalation process, a temperature dependent measurement has been performed. To prevent the

Figure 4.11: N 1s XPS of 2H-TPP monolayer evaporated on Al(111) at 180 K (blue) and annealed at increasing temperatures. At 180 K (blue) the molecule is protonated as can be seen by the presence of two N components. Increasing the temperature the metalation starts and completes around 420 K (single peak at 399.1 eV). At this temperature a small peak appears at 396.9 eV, related to AlN, and became dominant at higher temperature, when the molecule is decomposed.

metalation process, the sample has been cooled at 180 K before the evaporation of the 2H-TPP molecules and the N 1s XPS spectrum has been recorded at different temperatures.

Figure 4.11 shows the N 1s XPS spectra for a 2H-TPP monolayer on Al(111) in the 180 ÷ 570 K temperature range. In the spectrum at 180 K are visible the two N component relative to the iminic (400.4 eV) and pyrrolic (398.4 eV) components, indicating that the macrocycle is still protonated and the molecule is not metalated. Increasing the temperature, the intensity of these two peaks start decreasing, while a new peak arises at 399.1 eV, indicating the formation of a metallo-porphyrin. The metalation process completes at \sim 420 K. However, at this temperature a peak appears at 396.9 eV: its binding energy is compatible with aluminium nitride (AlN) and while its intensity increases with temperature the metalated molecule N peak decreases correspondingly. This behaviour suggests that at these temperatures the molecule decompose, with the breaking of the macrocycle and the bonding of its

Figure 4.12: C 1s XPS for 2H-TTP on Al(111). In the case of multilayer at 300 K (purple) a single peak is present at 285.25 eV which is shifted to 285 eV for the monolayer at 300 K (blue). The annealing of the monolayer at 370 K (green), 470 K (yellow) and 570 K (red) shows the appearance of new peaks; the dominant one, at 282.15 eV, can be related to aluminium carbide.

fragments to the Al surface.

Carbon 1s XPS (Figure 4.12) confirms the decomposition hypothesis. In the case of the multilayer at RT a single peak is present at 285.25 eV, while for the monolayer, as seen for the case of Ag(111), there is a shift of 0.25 eV towards lower binding energies (BE of 285 eV). Increasing the temperature, a new peak appears at 282.15 eV, which can be associated to aluminium carbide (AlC); some other peaks are also visible at higher temperatures, probably related to the presence of molecules fragments on the surface.

For a more precise indication on the occurrence of these transitions, a temperature dependent measurement has been performed, recording a rapid succession of N 1s XPS spectra, while annealing a 2H-TTP monolayer deposited at 190 K on Al(111). We have focused in the temperature range 190 ÷ 420 K in which the transitions occur. The metalation process, in which the macrocycle deprotonate and the molecule metalates, occurs between 250 K and 300 K, while the molecule

Figure 4.13: Temperature resolved N 1s XPS during annealing, up to 420 K, a 2H-TPP monolayer on Al(111) deposited at 190 K. It is clear the transition from two peaks (iminic at 398.4 eV and pyrrolic at 400.4 eV) to the Al-TPP single peak at 399.1 eV (4 N atoms of the molecule bond to Al) in the range 250÷300 K. Starting from 300÷350 K, the peak correspondent to aluminium nitride (AlN) appears at 396.9 eV.

Figure 4.14: C K-edge NEXAFS for 2H-TTP monolayer on Al(111) at different temperatures. Increasing the temperature, the reduction, in s polarization, of the peak at 284 eV indicates the flattening of the macrocycle. The increase of the dichroism with temperature for the peak at 285 eV, indicates a rotation toward the surface normal of the phenyl rings.

decomposition starts at $\sim 300 \div 350$ K. This indicates that the metalation of the porphyrins on the Al surface, together with the extremely high reactivity of the substrate, strongly affects their chemical stability. The Al-TTP molecule exists and can be realized on the surface, but its range of stability is quite limited.

To determine the adsorption geometry of 2H-TTP monolayer deposited on Al(111) during the annealing process we have used the dependence of NEXAFS from the linear polarization of the light to investigate the electronic transitions to the molecular empty states. In Figure 4.15 are shown the NEXAFS spectra at the N K-edge at different temperatures. For the assignment of the peaks we have referred to the work by Polzonetti and co-workers [33]. The first feature at lower photon energies (~ 398 eV) is related to electronic transitions from the iminic N atoms, while the other (~ 400 eV) is due to the pyrrolic (NH) atoms.

The spectrum at 300 K indicates a distortion of the macrocycle: while the iminic peak is almost suppressed for the s-polarization, indicating that the π orbitals of this atom are perpendicular to the surface, the dichroic signal of the other absorption peak indicates that the pyrrolic unit is bended with respect to the surface plane. At this temperature the molecules starts to metalate but the major fraction is still protonated: the presence of the hydrogen atoms could explain this distortion, as

Figure 4.15: NEXAFS for 2H-TTP monolayer on Al(111) at the N K absorption threshold. The decreasing with the temperature of the absorption peak at 400 eV indicates again the flattening of the molecule macrocycle at 470 K. The absence of absorption features at 570 K indicates the decomposition of the molecule.

a consequence of their steric hindrance. Actually, increasing the temperature, together with the metalation of the molecules, the peak intensity for s-polarization decreases; at 470 K, when the metalation is completed, the macrocycle is flat and parallel to the substrate surface. A second hypothesis is that the peak at 400 eV corresponds to a π^* transition for the metalated molecule and its decreasing in intensity is due to a different step of the metalation process. In this case, initially the N atoms in the macrocycle could be distorted toward an Al atom of the surface, and once the thermal energy is sufficient to overcome the energy barrier, the atom leaves the surface and the macrocycle metalates adopting a flat conformation. In the spectrum at 570 K the molecular features are no longer visible as a consequence of the porphyrin decomposition.

Carbon K-edge NEXAFS (Figure 4.14) confirms the macrocycle distortion at 300 K and its flattening at higher temperatures, as it is visible by the decreasing with temperature of the peak at 284 eV in s-polarization. Furthermore, a change in the dichroism of the second absorption peak (285 K), related to the phenyl rings, is visible. This indicates that, with the increasing of temperature, the phenyl rings rotate perpendicularly to the macrocycle and the substrate. Probably this adaptation is accompanied by an increasing in the molecule-substrate distance, which could also explain the successive flattening of the macrocycle, as a consequence of the extraction of an Al atom from the substrate, after an initial phase in which the macrocycle is bent toward the surface.

MnTPPCL on Al(111)

We have seen that the metalation process occurring at the Al surface can modify substantially the absorption geometry of the porphyrin molecules. To exclude the effects of the metal picking-up on the molecular configuration and to focus on the substrate influence we have deposited pre-synthesized metallo-porphyrins on the Al substrate. In particular a multilayer and monolayer of Mn(III)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin-Cl (MnTPPCL) has been evaporated on Al(111) single crystal at RT and then annealed at 570 K, as in the case of 2H-TPP.

Figures 4.16(a) and 4.16(b) reports C 1s and N 1s core level XPS, respectively, for monolayer and multilayer of MnTPPCL on Al(111). The appearance of the aluminium carbide and nitride peaks after the annealing process demonstrates that the decomposition of the molecules happens also in the absence of the on-surface metalation process. The annealing process at 520 ÷ 550 K of 2H-TPP on Ag(111) and Au(111) promotes the dehydrogenation reaction of the macrocycle with the formation of new C-C bonds and the flattening of the phenyl rings; anyway, in the latter case, the molecules, due to the weak interaction with the substrate, are also subjected to sublimation, leaving the Au surface. In the case of Al(111) instead, due to the high reactivity of this substrate, the annealing process at the

same temperature, both in the case of self-metalating porphyrin (2H-TPP) and pre-synthesized metallo-porphyrin (MnTPPCL), results in the decomposition of the molecule.

For comparison, Figures 4.17(a) and 4.17(b) reports the NEXAFS at the C and N K threshold, respectively, for MnTPPCL on Al(111) as deposited at 300 K and after annealing at 570 K. It is interesting to note that, while the C absorption spectrum at 300 K is quite similar to the case of 2H-TPP, in the case of N K NEXAFS the presynthesized metallo-porphyrin deposited at 300 K has a flat macrocycle: while the 2H-TPP NEXAFS at this temperature shows a distortion of the macrocycle towards the surface, in this case, the presence of the Mn atom inside the macrocycle stabilize the molecular framework, as it happens, instead, in the case of 2H-TPP at 470 K, when the molecule is metalated, forming Al-TPP. This evidence corroborates the hypothesis of an initial macrocycle distortion in the case of 2H-TPP just before the metal coordination, with the bending of the N atoms toward an Al atom on the surface, and the subsequent flattening once the metal ion is coordinated. Moreover, it confirms that, on Al(111), the occurrence of the metalation process on the substrate strongly modifies the geometry of the porphyrin molecule, affecting its chemical stability. Finally, it can be noted that, while the N K NEXAFS at 570 K has no recognisable features, the C K absorption edge still shows some defined peaks; at this temperature XPS reveals that the molecules undergo a decomposition, so, as pointed out in the case of 2H-TPP, these could be related to molecule fragments on the surface.

4.4 Effects of metalation on the molecule-substrate interaction

In TPP molecules, the phenyl groups and their orientation with respect to the macrocycle affect the distance between the molecule and the substrate, which, in turn, determines the charge transfer properties of the system. Moreover, the orientation of the meso-substituents play a crucial role in the mechanism of metalation of the molecule and the formation of metal-organic complexes.

As seen in the previous sections, the phenyl rings of 2H-TPP molecule on Au(111) and Ag(111) adopt a flat conformation when annealed above 525 K. In this case, the occurrence of a dehydrogenation process with the formation of new C-C bonds results in a lower distance between the molecule and the substrate, in a configuration similar to a phthalocyanine [21], in which the molecule-substrate distance is less than 3 Å. It has been observed [34] that the presence of the metal in the TPP macrocycle does not affect the supramolecular order in the monolayer deposited at room temperature. At this point, it is interesting to investigate the

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Figure 4.16: (a) C 1s XPS for MnTPP/Al(111) monolayer (top) and multilayer (bottom) on Al(111) as deposited at 300 K and after annealing at 570 K. After annealing the peak related to MnTPP/Al(111) decreases and new features appear. In particular the component at 282.15 eV, correspondent to aluminium carbide; for comparison at the bottom is reported the spectrum of C contaminated Al(111) surface. (b) N 1s XPS for MnTPP/Al(111) monolayer (top) and multilayer (bottom) on Al(111) as deposited at 300 K and after annealing at 570 K. After annealing the peak related to MnTPP/Al(111) decreases and a new component at 282.15 eV appears. This corresponds to aluminium nitride; for comparison at the bottom is reported the spectrum of N contaminated Al(111) surface.

Figure 4.17: (a) C K-edge NEXAFS for MnTPP multilayer (purple) and monolayer (blue) on Al(111) at 300 K and the monolayer after annealing at 570 K. The monolayer at 300 K (blue) is quite similar to the case of 2H-TPP. The absorption features at 570 K (red) indicates still the presence of molecule fragments on the surface after the decomposition. (b) N K-edge NEXAFS for MnTPP multilayer (purple) and monolayer (blue) on Al(111) at 300 K and the monolayer after annealing at 570 K. Differently from the case of 2H-TPP, for the MnTPP monolayer at 300 K (blue) the macrocycle is flat and not distorted. This indicates the N atoms in the empty 2H-TPP, without a metal coordination, tends to bend toward the surface. The absence of absorption features at 570 K (red) indicates the decomposition of the molecule.

Figure 4.18: N 1s XPS of (from top to bottom) 2H-TPP monolayer (blue), CoTPP monolayer (purple), 2H-TPP metalated at RT with Co (Co-TPP RT, green) and 2H-TPP annealed at 525 K and then metalated with Co (Co-TPP 525 K, orange). 2H-TPP as deposited shows the two iminic and pyrrolic components (397.9 eV and 399.9 eV respectively). CoTPP and Co-TPP RT are equivalent in line-shape and energy position (398.5 eV). The molecule metalated after annealing shows instead a shift for the N component of 0.1 eV (398.4 eV) indicating a stronger interaction with the substrate.

influence of the metal ion inside the molecule on its adsorption on the surface and the effects it produces in the interaction of the molecule with the substrate when annealed.

In particular, the correlation between the presence of the metal ion and the geometry and conformational adaptation of the molecule can be determined considering the effects of the annealing procedure, with a systematic procedure, in three different cases: (i) 2H-TPP annealed at 525 K and then metalated; (ii) 2H-TPP metalated and then annealed at 525 K; (iii) pre-synthesized transition metal-porphyrin (TM-TPP) annealed at 525 K.

In Figure 4.18 are reported the N 1s XPS spectra for the three cases, in which the metalation has been performed with Co, together with the spectrum of as deposited 2H-TPP before any annealing or metalation. Co(II)-tetra-phenylporphyrin (CoTPP) exists as a pure compound without any stabilizing ligand, making this molecule an ideal case of study. Moreover, as in the case of Cu [23], Co atoms can coordinate with the TPP macrocycle without requiring any annealing, which instead is needed, for example, in the case of Zn [20].

The Co metalation can be monitored by following the changes in the line-shape of N 1s XPS peaks [2]: 2H-TPP monolayer has the characteristic two peaks, at BE of 399.9 eV and 397.9 eV, of the pyrrolic and iminic components, respectively, while the metalated molecules show a single component. As can be seen, as deposited CoTPP and Co-TPP obtained by metalation at RT show the same shape and energy position (BE=398.5 eV), indicating that the two molecules are, in fact, equivalent. Differently, the XPS N 1s peak of the Co-TPP obtained after the annealing of the free-base 2H-TPP is shifted by ~ 0.1 eV towards lower binding energies, indicating a stronger interaction with the substrate.

NEXAFS spectra at the C K-edge can give a more clear understanding of the molecular conformation and geometry in the three cases. Figure 4.19 reports the absorption spectra before and after the metalation process. At first sight, it is evident that the annealing process of the free-base 2H-TPP monolayer at 575 K is determinant in changing the geometry assumed by the molecules, with the reorientation of the phenyl ring. Surprisingly, in the case of metalated molecules, the absorption structure is much less modified after the annealing process, and, notably, the phenyl rings do not rotate in this case, as can be seen by the presence of the resonance at 285 eV in s-polarization. The presence of the metal atom inhibits the rotation of the phenyl rings and prevents the conformational adaptation of the porphyrin molecule. It can be noted that the spectra for the pristine CoTPP and the metalated Co-TPP are identical indicating that the two molecules are equivalent and the metalation process is reliable.

Similarly, Figure 4.20 reports N K-edge NEXAFS for the same systems, before and after the metalation. Interestingly, it can be noted that, in the metalated molecules, the presence of a small peak in s-polarization for the first absorption resonance indicates a slight distortion of the macrocycle due to the presence of the metal atom. This feature almost disappears in the case of pre-annealed 2H-TPP. In this case the phenyl rings are flat and form an additional chemical bond with the macrocycle. The coordination with a metal atom is much less effective in distorting such a macrocycle structure, in which the pyrrolic units are now much more constrained by the bonding framework.

The flat conformation of the metalated TPP is a consequence of the conformational adaptation of the free base molecule after annealing, before the metalation. On the contrary, the metal coordination does not allow a more flat configuration of the phenyl rings, which remain rotated after the annealing at the same temperature. In the TPP, the molecule-substrate interaction is mainly driven by the π orbitals located on the phenyl rings. The presence of the metal atom in the macrocycle strongly affects this interaction, through the superposition of the Co d_z^2 orbitals with the substrate sp bands.

XPS of the valence band region can give an insight into the molecule-substrate interaction. Figure 4.21 reports the valence band (VB) spectra of the three case

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Figure 4.19: C K-edge NEXAFS for 2H-TTP annealed at 525 K (top left) and then metalated with Co (top right); 2H-TTP metalated at RT (middle left) and then annealed at 525 K (top right); CoTPP as evaporated (bottom left) and annealed at 525 K (bottom right). The presence of the phenyl absorption resonance in s-polarization after annealing indicates that the presence of the metal atom prevents the rotation of the phenyl rings and the consequent conformational adaptation of the molecule.

Figure 4.20: N K-edge NEXAFS for 2H-TTP annealed at 525 K (top left) and then metalated with Co (top right); 2H-TTP metalated at RT (middle left) and then annealed at 525 K (top right); CoTPP as evaporated (bottom left) and annealed at 525 K (bottom right). The disappearance of the peak in s-polarization in the case of pre-annealed metalated molecule (top right) indicates that the macrocycle, after the formation of the new bonds with the phenyl rings, is less affected by distortion due to the metal coordination.

Figure 4.21: Valence band XPS for Ag(111) (gray), 2H-TPP deposited at RT (blue) and annealed at 525 K (yellow), CoTPP annealed at 525 K (purple) and 2H-TPP annealed at 525 K and then metalated with Co (orange). The feature that appears at the Fermi level after the metalation is related to the interaction of the Co d_z^2 orbitals and the sp band of the substrate. The overall increasing in the intensity of the flat phenyl rings case with respect to the rotated case is due to the stronger interaction of the molecule with the substrate.

under study in the first 5 eV below the Fermi level, together with the spectra of the free base 2H-TPP and the bare Ag(111) substrate for comparison. The comparison of the metal-free TPP spectra, shows an increasing in the density of states in the region near the Fermi level after the annealing process. This indicates a stronger interaction of the molecular π orbitals, located on the macrocycle and the phenyl rings, with the Ag substrate band.

Once the molecules are metalated, a peak appears in the immediate vicinity of the Fermi level edge, due to an overlap between the Co and the Ag bands, which characterizes the presence of the metal in the macrocycle [21, 32]. As can be seen by the comparison of these two spectra, the metalation of a previously annealed 2H-TPP at 525 K results in a stronger intensity of the filled states near the Fermi level, *i.e.* the HOMOs between 0 and 3 eV, with respect to the CoTPP annealed at the same temperature. The stronger interaction between the metallo-porphyrin and the Ag underneath is generated by the charge transfer from the substrate to the molecule and mostly involves the Co d_z^2 orbitals [35], as a consequence of the increased hybridization of Co and Ag states due to a shorter bond distance. It is worth noting that the geometrical adaptation of the tetra-phenyl-porphyrin in the monolayer has no implications on the possible hypothesis for the metalation mechanism. The metalation of other macrocycle molecules, with different

geometries, is indeed happening in a similar way [2, 5, 6, 16, 36]. Therefore, the metalation process can be explained by a simple ad-atom hopping instead of a substrate surface-mediated diffusion to the reaction sites.

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Chapter 5

Magnetic properties of Metal Porphyrins

5.1 Introduction

Recently, magnetic coupling of self-assembled organic monolayers with metal substrates has raised increasing attention and the control of exchange coupling across this molecule-substrate interface is a key issue in the field of molecular spintronics [1–5]. The interaction of spin-polarized electrons in the molecular and surface orbitals, through the formation of interface states, could induce a magnetic ordering in paramagnetic molecules, even above room temperature. Recent developments in the field of surface magnetism, with the possible applications of some paramagnetic 3*d* metal-organic macrocycle molecules as switchable elements in molecular spintronic devices, have generated much interest into the structural and magnetic properties of these molecules [6–26].

Considering metal-porphyrins and phthalocyanines, in order to stabilize their magnetic moment against thermal fluctuations, the deposition on ferromagnetic films is required to efficiently allow the magnetic coupling of the metal molecular centres with the surface magnetization. One fundamental question is in which way the metallo-porphyrins interact with ferromagnetic surfaces. A number of consistent surface-magnetism experiments confirm that the coupling between the first molecular layer and the substrate originates from exchange interaction [10–13, 27–29].

In an unperturbed case, for a single layer of metallo-porphyrins, the 3*d* metal atom at the centre of the macrocycle would be at $\sim 0.25 \div 0.5$ nm above an atomically flat substrate. This is probably too far for a direct exchange coupling through an overlap of the orbitals. Therefore, indirect exchange coupling through delocalized electrons on the phenyl or ethyl substituents should be considered. On

the other hand, a possible direct exchange coupling due to a distortion of the macrocycle or particular conformations of the molecule may be kept in mind. It is worth noting that, on the Ag(111) substrate, the overlap between the d_{z^2} orbital of Fe or Co atoms at the centre of the macrocycle and the sp states of silver was observed by photoemission experiments [30].

A technique such as XMCD has several advantages over other techniques, because it is chemically selective (i.e. you know the probed chemical element since you are measuring a core level threshold) and it can be sensitive to just a single layer of molecules. For example, this technique has been used to study the magnetic ordering induced on molecular monolayers of MnTPPCl and Fe(III)-octaethyl-porphyrin-Cl (FeOEPCl) deposited on a Co and Ni thin film substrates [8, 10, 15], as well as one monolayer of CoTPP adsorbed on Ni film [13]. These studies show that the CoTPP, MnTPPCl and the FeOEPCl molecules present a ferromagnetic coupling to the substrate film, having a remanent magnetization in the same direction of the substrate magnetization.

In the case of Co substrate, cooling the sample to 85 K did not get a large increase in the dichroic signal observed at RT [8], indicating that the magnetization of iron ions in the molecule is close to saturation already at room temperature. This excludes the dipole-dipole interaction as a mechanism of spin magnetic coupling, because, at such high temperature, the paramagnetic saturation would require unreasonably large magnetic fields at the molecular site, much higher than that used in these works.

Furthermore, in the work of Wende and co-workers [11] it is suggested that the size of the XMCD for 1.5 ML is basically identical to the one of 1 ML. This seems to indicate that the additional 0.5 ML does not contribute to any magnetic signal. Therefore, their conclusion is that only the first molecular monolayer couples magnetically to the ferromagnetic film, while the second layer is decoupled from the substrate.

5.2 Monolayer magnetic coupling: the case of MnTPP-Cl on Fe(110)

We started investigating the magnetic properties of a single layer of porphyrins on a ferromagnetic substrate. In order to obtain a metal substrate with controlled magnetic properties we have epitaxially grown an ultra-thin Fe film by electron beam evaporation on a Cu(110) single crystal, previously cleaned by Ar ion sputtering and annealing cycles. The thickness of the film has been chosen to be approximately 10 ML in order to obtain an in-plane easy magnetization axes. A MnTPPCl multilayer has been evaporated in UHV on the Fe film, kept at room

temperature, by sublimating the molecules at 550 K. Then the sample has been annealed at 570 K for 5 minutes to obtain a monolayer, as described in Chapter 3. The sample has been magnetized in UHV by applying an external magnetic field of approximately 1 T and the measurements were made in remanence. X-ray absorption spectroscopy measurements were performed at the BACH beamline at the Elettra synchrotron.

Figure 5.1 shows absorption spectra at the Fe $L_{2,3}$ edge for left and right circular polarized light in grazing incidence geometry (angle of 60° between the photon wave vector and the surface normal), after the magnetization. The dichroism indicates that the Fe film is magnetized. The absence of a dichroic signal in the off normal geometry confirms that the easy magnetization axis of the Fe film is parallel to the substrate surface.

At this point we have a ferromagnetic substrate with a precise magnetization, defined in direction and intensity by the XAS at the Fe edge, thus we can probe the magnetic coupling of the molecular layer adsorbed on it, in particular by looking at the absorption threshold of the metallic atom inside the molecule macrocycle.

In figure 5.2 are reported the absorption spectra at grazing incidence of the Mn $L_{2,3}$ edge for the MnTPPCL monolayer on Fe/Cu(110). Quite surprisingly, the dichroic signal is opposite to that of the Fe film, indicating that the Mn atoms inside the molecules have an anti-parallel magnetic coupling with the magnetization of the substrate, or, in other words, the coupling of the Mn spin is anti-ferromagnetic with respect to the Fe substrate. A fundamental point to note here is that the evaporated molecule, namely Mn(III)TPPCL, has a Cl atom attached to the Mn ion to stabilize the molecule (as already discussed in a previous section) and the Mn atom is in the +3 oxidation state. The presence of Cl on the surface is confirmed by XPS both in the case of the evaporated multilayer and after the annealing process to obtain the monolayer. On the other hand, the line-shape of Mn does not correspond to Mn(III) oxidation state, but instead to Mn(II) [31], as can also be seen comparing it with the Figure 5.6, which reports the Mn absorption spectra for the Mn(II)TPP molecule. A possible explanation is that once the Mn(III)TPPCL molecule is adsorbed, the Cl atom detach from Mn and remains on the surface, while the molecule, now in the form Mn(II)TPP, is stabilized by the presence of the substrate, as it happens for *in-situ* metalated MnTPP and FeTPP.

The presence of the Cl atom may be of fundamental importance in determining the magnetic properties of the molecular film, possibly playing a role similar to that of NO for CoTPP and FeTPP [13, 19, 32]. In that case, on addition of NO, the formation of a nitrosil complex suppress the magnetic moment of the molecule, which can be restored by thermal dissociation with an annealing treatment. Preliminary DFT calculations [[13]] confirm the anti-ferromagnetic coupling with the substrate magnetization of the Mn atoms in the molecule layer. Moreover, the coupling is predicted to be anti-parallel independently on the presence or absence

Figure 5.1: XAS and XMCD spectra at the L_{2,3} edge of Fe for a 10 ML thick film. The measurements were made at grazing incidence (60° from the normal) with the remnant magnetization in-plane. The dichroic signal indicates the in-plane magnetization of the Fe film.

of the Cl atom bonded to the Mn atom.

5.3 Magnetic coupling of the second layer: MnTPP on FeTPP on Fe(110)

Here, we investigate the *in-situ* prepared second layer of metalated Mn(II)-tetraphenyl-porphyrin (Mn-TPP) deposited on 1 ML of metalated Fe-TPP, grown on a film of Fe/Cu(110). For the adsorbed Mn-TPP molecules we will study the molecular orientation, the electronic structure and, most importantly, the magnetic properties and exchange coupling between the molecules and the ferromagnetic film. This is achieved using XAS, XPS and XMCD measurements, in combination with the theoretical calculations of the electronic structure and the magnetic exchange coupling. L-edge XAS provides a unique element-selective probe of the bonding and magnetic properties of transition-metal ions, with the further advantage of extreme sensitivity to surface-dilute systems. This is of crucial importance for the present study, since the coverage of 1 ML of Mn-TPP molecules

Figure 5.2: XAS and XMCD spectra at the L_{2,3} edge of Mn for a monolayer of MnTPPCI on Fe film with in plane magnetization. The measurements were made at grazing incidence (60° from the normal), with the remnant magnetization in-plane, for the two light polarizations. The dichroic signal opposite to that of the Fe film indicates that the Mn atoms are coupled anti-ferromagnetically with the substrate magnetization.

Figure 5.3: XMCD spectra at the $L_{2,3}$ edge at the Fe threshold for a 10 ML iron film on Cu(110). The measurements were made at grazing incidence (60° from the normal) with remnant magnetization in-plane

corresponds to an effective Mn coverage of 0.02-0.03 ML.

It is demonstrated that, owing to a direct super-exchange interaction, which provides robust anti-ferromagnetic properties for the second layer of molecules, the easy axis of magnetization is reversed for Mn-TPP from the in plane Fe magnetization of the first Fe-TPP layer deposited on Fe/Cu(110).

5.3.1 Results

A thin film (10 ML) of Fe has been evaporated at RT on a Cu(110) single crystal. As grown, this film is non-magnetic, but can be magnetized with an external magnetic field and measured in remanence. The $L_{2,3}$ edge spectrum of Fe, after the exposition to a magnetic field of 1 T, is shown in Figure 5.3. Because the easy axis of magnetization is in-plane for this Fe film, the measurements were made at grazing incidence (60° off the normal). By changing the circular polarization, from left to right, the $L_{2,3}$ edge of Fe shows a clear dichroism as a consequence of the remanent magnetization. Spectra taken at normal incidence do not present any dichroism, confirming that the magnetization vector lies parallel to the substrate surface.

A monolayer of 2H-TPP has then been deposited at RT on this substrate. As

Figure 5.4: N 1s XPS spectra for subsequent Mn evaporation steps. First layer of FeTPP (blue), after evaporation of 2H-TPP second layer (purple), metalation of the second layer after Mn evaporation with 35% (light green) and 60% (green) of metalated molecules.

already shown [[1]], [33], the N 1s photoemission spectrum of this monolayer consists of one single peak, as reported in Figure 5.4. This is the clear confirmation that the four nitrogen atoms are now equivalent and coordinated with a metal atom, *i.e.* 2H-TPP molecules metalate by picking-up a Fe atom from the substrate.

In a hierarchical process, a three-dimensional supramolecular structure has been formed by the evaporation of an additional porphyrin single-layer on top of the already obtained Fe-TPP monolayer. The XPS spectrum, beside the single peak related to the first layer, shows the presence of two new N 1s peaks due to the additional layer, indicating that the molecules of the second layer are not metalated by the substrate (see Figure 5.4). As already demonstrated [34], the free-base molecules can then be metalated by the evaporation of metal atoms in UHV. The metalation process can be controlled following the evolution of N 1s spectra during the evaporation. In particular the intensity of the two nitrogen species of the free-base molecule is reduced upon metal evaporation, while a new component, whose intensity is proportional to the fraction of molecules coordinated with a metal atom, increases. The procedure was interrupted when about 60% of the molecules were metalated, in order to be sure that no Mn clusters were formed.

The Fe XAS spectrum of 10 ML Fe/Cu(100) exhibits broad L_3 and L_2 peaks typical of the metal, and the further deposition of 1 ML of 2H-TPP does not substantially change the spectrum, although we should expect that the so produced Fe-TPP should have a multiplet structure.

Anyway we can assume that the XMCD signal of the Fe-TPP ML formed on top of the Fe/Cu(110) substrate follows the substrate dichroism, *i.e.* the magnetization of the iron atom in Fe-TPP molecules is parallel to the substrate magnetization, as it happens in the case of 1 ML of FeOEPCl on Co and Ni films [12], or 1 ML of CoTPP on Ni substrate [13]. This is due to the direct exchange coupling between the substrate atoms and the Fe atom of the molecule, which aligns the molecular Fe spins along the magnetization orientation of the substrate.

There are several calculations of Fe-Porphyrin on Ni substrate demonstrating that the coupling between Ni atoms and Fe ions is ferromagnetic with an energy minimum at a Ni-Fe distance of 3.48 ± 0.01 Å [11, 22]. Similar ferromagnetic alignment was found for Mn-Porphyrin on Co in two adsorption states, physisorbed (calculated Co-Mn distance about 2.1 Å) and chemisorbed (calculated Co-Mn distance about 3.5 Å) [9].

We perform similar calculations using DFT. The model of a Fe-TPP monolayer on Fe(110) is reported in Figure 5.5. Structural relaxations of the molecules were obtained by optimizing the Hellmann-Feynman forces with a tolerance of 0.02 eV/Å. The Perdew-Wang generalised gradient approximation (GGA) was used for the exchange-correlation potential [35].

As shown in a previous publication [33], the porphyrins metalate at room temperature by picking-up a substrate atom with a minimum distance from the Fe

Figure 5.5: Density functional theory calculation for a 2HTPP monolayer on Fe(110). The molecule metalates picking-up an atom from the substrate with a minimum distance of 2.8 \AA between the Fe atom and the surface. The coupling is strongly ferromagnetic with a magnetic moment of $1.7 \mu_B$.

ion in the macrocycle and the substrate of $2.80 \pm 0.01 \text{ \AA}$. The resulting interaction is strongly ferromagnetic with a spin magnetic moment of $m_{Fe(TPP)} = 1.7 \mu_B$.

After the magnetization of the system, XMCD shows a clear dichroism of the Mn L_{2,3} edges, which is opposite to the dichroism observed for Fe L_{2,3} edges. This tells us that (i) the spin coupling extends to the second porphyrins layer and (ii) an anti-parallel ordering of Mn magnetic moments with respect to those of Fe is present.

The energy positions and the line-shape of the Mn L_{2,3} edges in XAS measurements are similar to those reported for Mn(II) [36]. This spectral shape, relative to the ligand-induced changes and localization of the Mn d-orbitals, indicates that coordination bonds were formed between Mn atoms and the macrocyclic N ligands, confirming that Mn(II) is at the centre of the macrocycle. XPS spectra of Mn 2p core levels also give the same indication, with energy positions and satellites typical of Mn(II) compounds (Figure 5.7).

Although we do not know exactly the relative position of the molecules of the second layer on the first monolayer, the direct bonds between Mn and Fe atoms is forbidden by the growth geometry of the porphyrins layers; a super-exchange interaction should then propagate through conjugated bond linkages,

Figure 5.6: XAS and XMCD at the Mn L_{2,3} edge for the MnTPP/FeTPP/Fe system, in the grazing incidence geometry. The dichroic signal, opposite to that of the substrate indicates an anti-ferromagnetic coupling of the second molecular layer with the substrate magnetization.

Figure 5.7: XPS of Mn 2p core level. The line-shape of the spectrum, with the presence of the two satellites at about 5 eV from the main peaks, confirms that the Mn atoms are in the 2+ oxidation state.

Figure 5.8: Energy difference between anti-ferromagnetic and ferromagnetic coupling for two molecular layers in function of the interlayer separation. The coupling is FM at lower distances and becomes AFM increasing the distance. The spin flip occurs at ~ 3.5 Å. The distance between two TPP layers is typically larger, thus confirming the possibility of AFM coupling.

which may also act as 2D molecular wires. Preliminary DFT calculations with GGA for a bilayer of porphyrin macrocycle adsorbed on a ferromagnetic substrate (Figure 5.8) has been performed. For smaller interlayer separation the coupling is ferromagnetic (FM) and becomes anti-ferromagnetic (AFM) as the separation increases, with a flip around 3.5 Å. Considering that the typical separation of two TPP layers is larger than this value, this result confirms that an AFM coupling is possible also if there is a direct interface between Mn and Fe ions in the two layers.

Experiments were carried out at the BACH beamline of the Elettra synchrotron radiation facility in Trieste. The Cu(110) metal substrate was cleaned by Ar⁺ ion sputtering at 1 KeV and annealing at 970 K. Fe layers on clean Cu(110) surface were deposited using an OMICRON electron-beam evaporator. The magnetization was performed by means of a permanent magnet of 1 T. 2H-TPP were deposited on the substrates kept at room temperature, from a home-made tantalum basket heated at 550 K by passage of current. Mn metalation of the 2H-TPP ML at RT was obtained by evaporating the Mn atoms by means of a TECTRA electron-beam evaporator. UHV conditions (in the pressure range of 10^{-10} mbar) were maintained throughout the experiment.

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Chapter 6

Conclusions and Outlook

The interaction between tetra-phenyl-porphyrins and the substrate is strongly related to their adsorption geometry on the surface. In Chapter 3 we have reported how these molecules are able to self-assemble on crystal surfaces producing long-range ordered structures. This is an interesting feature considering the ability of these molecules to coordinate to several metal ions: for example, it allows the fabrication of regular and equally spaced arrays of single metallic atoms on the surface with a lateral extension of the order of few nanometres, which is otherwise not achievable with conventional methods.

Moreover, the flexibility in the molecular chemical synthesis allows to tailor the structure of these molecules, by the addition of functional groups able to introduce new useful properties. The notable effect exerted by the presence of the phenyl rings in tetra-phenyl-porphyrins, beside its fundamental spacing action both from the surface and between the molecules, reveals in the conformational adaptation that the molecule undergoes upon annealing. The rotation of the phenyl rings towards the surface drives an essential modification of the chemical composition of the molecule, as proven in the case of TPP adsorbed on Au(111) and Ag(111).

The main mechanisms involved in this interactions are the hybridization of molecular states upon adsorption and the charge transfer from the substrate. The coordination of the molecule macrocycle with a metal atom strongly affects these mechanisms. As reported in Chapter 4, metal evaporation and picking-up of a substrate atom are the methods that allow the creation of metallo-porphyrins on metal substrates. Moreover, the mechanism of molecule metalation and the formation of metal-organic complexes is in turn determined by the orientation of the meso-substituents in tetra-phenyl-porphyrins. This essentially changes the molecule-substrate interaction as demonstrated in the case of TPP metalation with Co, for which the correlation between the presence of the metal ion and the geometry and conformational adaptation of the molecule is investigated.

As a consequence of the metalation process, the coordination of the macrocycle

with a metal ion can bring about a magnetic moment to the molecule. In Chapter 5 it is studied the magnetic coupling of a single layer of TPP on a ferromagnetic substrate. Moreover, taking advantage of the molecular self-assembly, we have been able to form a double layer square planar array of porphyrins at room temperature. Although individual molecules cannot be magnetized independently, this approach enables the fabrication of metal-organic molecular layers with stable magnetization at room temperature.

Despite the experimental and theoretical challenges, the creation of devices based on organic molecules is undoubtedly promising, while the research efforts in this sense are definitely of fundamental importance for a deeper comprehension of the world at the nano-scale.

Appendix A

List of Publications

Journal Articles

This thesis is based on part of the following peer-reviewed articles, which are referred to in the text by double square brackets:

- [[1]] M. Panighel, G. Di Santo, M. Caputo, A. Goldoni. **Review of 2H-tetra-phenyl-porphyrins metalation in ultra-high vacuum on metal surfaces.** *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 470, 012012 (2013). doi: [10.1088/1742-6596/470/1/012012](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/470/1/012012)

- [[2]] M. Marsili, P. Umari, G. Di Santo, M. Caputo, M. Panighel, A. Goldoni, M. Kumar, M. Pedio. **Solid state effects on the electronic structure of H2OEP.** *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 16, 27104 (2014) doi: [10.1039/c4cp03450c](https://doi.org/10.1039/c4cp03450c)

- [[3]] C. Struzzi, N.I. Verbitskiy, A.V. Fedorov, A. Nefedov, O. Frank, M. Kalbac, G. Di Santo, M. Panighel, A. Goldoni, J. Gärtner, W. Weber, M. Weinl, M. Schreck, Ch. Wöll, H. Sachdev, A. Grüneis, L. Petaccia. **A multi-spectroscopic and microscopic characterization of graphene on single crystal Ir(111) films on Si(111) wafers.** *Carbon* 81, 167 (2015) doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2014.09.045](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2014.09.045)

- [[4]] M. Caputo, M. Panighel, L. Petaccia, G. Di Santo, C. Struzzi, A. Goldoni. **Metallic picene/C60 heterojunctions let continuous alkali metal doping of C60.** *Phys. Rev. B* 90, 201401(R) (2014) doi: [10.1103/PhysRevB.90.201401](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.90.201401)

- [[5]] M. Caputo, M. Panighel, G. Di Santo, C. Struzzi, P. Parisse, L. Petaccia, L. Floreano, A. Verdini, B. Taleatu, C. Lal, A. Goldoni. **Experimental**

study of pristine and alkali metal doped picene layers: confirmation of the insulating phase in multilayer doped compounds. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 116, 19902 (2012). doi: [10.1021/jp306640z](https://doi.org/10.1021/jp306640z)

- [[6]] E. Ferrari, L. Galli, E. Miniussi, M. Morri, M. Panighel, M. Ricci, P. Lacovig, S. Lizzit, A. Baraldi. **Layer-dependent Debye temperature of Ru(0001) by means of high-energy resolution core-level photoelectron spectroscopy.** *Physical Review B* 82, 195420 (2010). doi: [10.1103/PhysRevB.82.195420](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.82.195420)

Other publications, based on the results of this thesis, are in preparation:

- [[9]] M. Panighel, G. Di Santo, A. Goldoni. **Drift corrections of scanning probe microscopy images by Fourier analysis.** (Section [2.1.2](#))
- [[10]] M. Panighel, M. Caputo, G. Di Santo, L. Floreano, A. Verdini, A. Cossaro, A. Goldoni. **Conformational adaptation of 2H-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin on Au(111).** (Section [3.3](#))
- [[11]] G. Zamborlini, G. Di Santo, A. Goldoni, M. Panighel, V. Feyer, C. M. Schneider. **Highly oriented self-assembly domains of Co and Ni-TPP on the Cu (100) surface: multitechnique approach to study the electronic and geometric structure.** (Section [3.2.2](#))
- [[12]] M. Panighel, M. Caputo, G. Di Santo, L. Floreano, A. Verdini, A. Cossaro, A. Goldoni. **Conformational adaptation and metalation of 2H-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin on Al(111).** (Section [4.3.2](#))
- [[13]] A. Goldoni, M. Panighel, M. Caputo, G. Di Santo, C. Castellarin-Cudia, M. Fanetti, F. Bondino, E. Magnano, N. Stojic, N. Binggeli. **Anti-parallel magnetic coupling of manganese tetra-phenyl-porphyrin to a ferromagnetic iron substrate.** (Section [5.2](#))
- [[14]] M. Panighel, M. Caputo, G. Di Santo, C. Castellarin-Cudia, M. Fanetti, F. Bondino, E. Magnano, N. Stojic, N. Binggeli, A. Goldoni. **Changes in remanent magnetization by designing supramolecular metalated porphyrins arrays on 3d magnetic substrates.** (Section [5.3](#))

Appendix B

Symbols and Abbreviations

2H-TPP	2H-5,10,15,20-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin
2H-OEP	2H-octa-ethyl-porphyrin
AFM	anti-ferromagnetic
BE	binding energy
CoTPP	Co(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin
DFT	density functional theory
FeOEPCI	Fe(III)-octa-ethyl-porphyrin-Cl
Fe-TPP	Fe(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin
FFT	fast Fourier transform
FM	ferromagnetic
HOMO	highest occupied molecular orbital
LDOS	local density of states
ML	monolayer
Mn-TPP	Mn(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin
MnTPPCI	Mn(III)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin-Cl
NEXAFS	Near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure
NiTPP	Ni(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin

RT	room temperature
RuTPP	Ru(II)-tetra-phenyl-porphyrin
TPP	tetra-phenyl-porphyrin
UHV	ultra high vacuum
STM	scanning tunnelling microscopy
VB	valence band
XAS	X-ray absorption spectroscopy
XMCD	X-ray magnetic circular dichroism
XPS	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

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